

Flexigy: Applying the Flex Offer concept to smart-grid energy management

ISEP – Instituto Superior de Engenharia do Porto

2020 / 2021

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Degree in Informatics Engineering

July 2021

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« Failure is an option here. If things are not failing, you are not innovating enough. »

Elon Musk

Acknowledgments

First, I would like to thank my parents and grandparents for their love, caring, and sacrifices for educating and preparing me for the future. Without them, I would not have become the person I am today. Also, I express my thanks to my girlfriend and friends for always supporting me and for pushing me to achieve my dreams.

I want to express my deep and sincere gratitude to my internship advisor, professor Luis Miguel Moreira Lino Ferreira, and to my internship co-advisor, professor Paulo Manuel Baltarejo de Sousa, for always being available to provide me invaluable guidance and knowledge throughout the internship project, despite the adverse conditions verified due to the Covid-19 pandemic. It proved to be a wonderful learning experience that helped me to grow personally and become a more professional developer.

Furthermore, I want to thank everyone at Instituto Superior da Universidade do Porto for giving me the tools and opportunity to pursue my goals.

And last but certainly not least, I want to thank my friends and colleagues at ISEP for working and sharing their knowledge with me. A special thanks goes to my bachelor's teammates, João Vitorino, Pedro Pereira, and Tiago Dias, for all the moments spent together that contributed to my individual growth, either as a student or as a person.

Abstract

The electricity sector is facing major challenges in the implementation of renewable energies at a large scale. End users are taking on the role of electricity producers and consumers simultaneously, injecting excess electricity into the grid, hence difficulting the needed grid energy balance. The grid imbalance causes increasingly higher costs, which are later reflected in the tariffs paid by consumers, thus threatening the widespread of renewable energy sources.

The development of this project aims to contribute to the design and implementation of a solution to the grid balance problem. In order to achieve this goal, a platform was created to manage and optimize the user's energy flexibility (Flex Offers).

The implementation of energy optimization algorithms at the community level and the development of a feature to handle energy demand requests from network operators allow the developed system to successfully respond to the needs of the various players in the energy market value chain.

Keywords (Theme): Flex Offer, Renewable Energies, Smart Grids, Energy Flexibility

Keywords (Technologies): .Net Core, C#, Grafana, REST, SQL Server

Resumo

A transformação do sector elétrico está a encontrar grandes desafios na implementação de energias renováveis em larga escala. Os utilizadores finais assumem cada vez mais, simultaneamente, o papel de produtores e de consumidores de energia elétrica, injetando na rede elétrica o excesso de eletricidade não consumido, o que dificulta o necessário equilíbrio entre o consumo e a produção. O desequilíbrio da rede origina custos cada vez mais avultados, o que se reflete posteriormente nas tarifas pagas pelos consumidores, ameaçando assim a disseminação das energias renováveis.

O desenvolvimento deste projeto tem como objetivo contribuir para o desenho e implementação de uma solução que permita ajudar no equilíbrio energético das redes. De forma a atingir este objetivo, foi criada uma plataforma para a gestão e otimização da flexibilidade energética (Flex Offers) dos utilizadores que garante benefícios a todos os participantes no mercado de energia.

A implementação de algoritmos de otimização de energia ao nível comunitário e o desenvolvimento de uma funcionalidade para a gestão de pedidos dos operadores da rede permitem à plataforma desenvolvida responder às necessidades descritas e assim promover a adoção de energias renováveis.

Palavras-chave (Tema): Flex Offer, Energias Renováveis, Smart Grids, Flexibilidade Energética

Palavras-chave (Tecnologias): .Net Core, C#, Grafana, REST, SQL Server

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Notation and Glossary

.Net Core	Free, open-source, general-purpose development platform maintained by Microsoft used to build different types of applications
API	Application Programming Interface. A set of clearly defined methods of communication between various software components
C#	Multiparadigm Programming Language
DTO	A Data Transfer Object (DTO) is an object that is used to encapsulate data and send it from one subsystem of an application to another
EDM	Energy Demand Management (EDM)
Flex Offer	Concept describing energy consumption/production flexibility of an electrical device
ISEP	Instituto Superior de Engenharia do Porto
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
REST	Representational state transfer or RESTful Web services provide interoperability between computer systems on the Internet
Solar PV	Solar Photovoltaic panels
TSO	Transmission System Operator
UI	User Interface
UML	Unified Modeling Language, a software modeling language
VPS	Virtual Power Solutions (VPS), a Portuguese energy solutions company part of the project consortium
RGPD	General Data Protection Regulation, European Union law on data protection and privacy

1 Introduction

This introductory chapter presents an overview of the project's context, goals, approach, and planning.

1.1 Project Context

In recent years, with the cost of solar PV panels reaching record lows [1], many households are installing rooftop-based solar plants, consuming their energy production first, and later selling the surplus to the grid.

The high penetration of renewable sources into power grids results in difficulties maintaining the necessary grid balance [2]. For example, Solar PV produces all its energy during the day and none after sunset, when energy demand usually peaks. The time imbalance between peak demand and renewable energy production results in a bigger and more expensive energy production ramp-up of conventional power plants at sunset [3], [4], thus reducing both environmental and economic benefits of renewable energy sources [5].

The traditional alternative to solve both the over-generation and unbalance problems is to use excessive electricity production to support non-grid applications such as pumped-storage hydroelectricity [6]. Batteries, implemented at a large enough scale, can also help to flatten the curve fluctuation and maintain the voltage profile [7]–[10]. However, the cost of implementing battery storage at the needed scale is a major limiting factor of this solution [11].

The Flexibility concept is an experimental solution that proposes to increase grid balance by managing and optimizing energy resources based on their time and power flexibility. These platforms can shift the activation of devices in time according to their flexibility; they can also act by increasing or decreasing the power consumption of devices.

Among the consortium partners, Virtual Power Solutions (VPS) [13] is an innovative market leader in the design and operation of dynamic, connected platforms developed to minimize consumption by increasing energy efficiency, optimizing the time of use, and monetizing loads. Energia Simples [14], another consortium partner, is an energy services company headquartered in Portugal specializing in sustainability. It dedicates itself to the commercialization of green energy, research, and direct promotion of new renewable energy technologies and energy efficiency. ISEP is an academic institution with extensive experience

in leading and managing national and European projects while also having the proven knowledge necessary to develop the optimized scheduling and management algorithm.

The student motivation to engage in this internship arose from the opportunity to participate in the development of a significant contribution to the renewable smart grid while also developing problem-solving, research, and engineering skills by being at the forefront of future technologies.

1.1.1 Internship Goals

The goals for this internship are divided into two parts: transform the previous prototypes into a maintainable and scalable platform, solving many of its limitations, and accounting for future integration in the VPS systems; add new features to the Flexigy platform to satisfy the consortium ideas for the project. The following project goals (PG) were identified:

- PG 1. Implement the Flexigy web platform, accounting for system maintainability, scalability, performance, and ease of future integration with VPS systems while also designing and introducing new energy demand management concepts.
- PG 2. Architect, build and test the Flex Offers scheduling algorithms according to the defined consortium goals and business rules. These must apply the Flex Offer concept to optimize the local energy production and consumption of a house, a building, or an energy community.
- PG 3. Develop new algorithms to handle energy demand requests, namely, interruptibility and regulating reserve requests.
- PG 4. Build a service to operate devices according to the Flex Offer schedule, interruptibility requests, and regulate reserve service.
- PG 5. Implement a feature that automatically detects the building's unpredictable energy consumption based on historical consumption patterns.
- PG 6. Develop a way to visualize the various aspects of the application; most importantly, the Flex Offers scheduling.

1.1.2 Approach

The approach adopted in this project is somewhat conditioned by the internship time and by works and decisions already taken in the previous project implementations.

Considering the internship goals, the approach starts by rethinking and reengineering the existing system to improve its features and maintainability and incorporate new consortium ideas. For instance, a new design of the Flex Offer scheduling algorithms will be proposed, contemplating the consortium constraints and business model. Moreover, energy demand management solutions will be studied and explored in order to be implemented in the project.

No requirements specified the tools or technologies to be used, so, after careful analysis, .NET Core and Grafana were chosen to implement the solution back-end and front-end, respectively.

1.1.3 Contributions from this project

The Flexigy project presents an intelligent energy optimizing platform that tackles different players' economic and social needs in the energy market value chain.

The energy consumers could benefit from the platform's optimized device management based on their energy flexibility. This module helps lowering electricity prices according to each user preference and even provides financial compensations through the fulfillment of energy demand requests. If used commercially, the project can also generate profit for the aggregator company, in this case, VPS.

If approved by legislation, grid operators can use an intelligent module ready to receive and handle energy demand requests at a community level, aiming to minimize the energy imbalance problem and, consequently, the costs of introducing renewable energy in the grid.

Furthermore, this proof of concept encourages the use of renewable energy sources, mainly solar PV panels, since it helps producers reduce the investment pay-out time by selling the energy surplus to the community at a profitable price.

Ultimately, society itself could benefit from the solutions provided by this pilot, as it reduces electricity prices to end-users while promoting the widespread adoption of renewable energy sources.

1.2 Project Planning

Rational Unified Process (RUP) system was the selected process to plan the project tasks. RUP is an iterative software development methodology that aims to produce high-quality software that meets the needs of its end-users within a predictable schedule and time [15]. This system holds the developers responsible for their tasks and completion times [16]. The initial project planning can be found in Appendix A.

In the Gantt diagram in Figure 1, it is possible to verify the development process of the solution throughout the internship and analyze the time necessary to accomplish each task.

Figure 1 - Gantt Diagram

As shown in Figure 1, the internship project started with a study of the existing work and documentation related to the Flexigy project. Then, the key theoretical concepts and some other solutions with similar purposes to those of this project were explored. Next, the functional and non-functional requirements were studied, leading to the definition of the business rules and domain constraints. Afterward, the system design was carried out following the best software practices. Finally, system tests were conducted to evaluate the implementation of the system features. This report was written throughout the whole solution development process.

1.2.1.1 Meetings

Microsoft Teams was the tool used by the team to meet during the internship. The meets were used to plan the project, discuss platform design, and demonstrate the work done throughout the weeks. Additionally, the consortium Microsoft Teams tool was used to present the solution milestones to the stakeholders as well as discuss implementation details.

1.3 Report Structure

This section presents the report's structure and a short description of each chapter's and subchapter's contents.

- **Chapter 2 - State-of-the-art:** This chapter focuses on explaining the problem's context and previous implementations while also detailing related project implementations that may have tackled the same issue or were influential for this project design.
- **Chapter 3 - Requirements Engineering and Analysis:** This chapter outlines the project requirements and the business model analysis.
- **Chapter 4 - Design:** This chapter describes the design decisions and documentation for every feature in the project.
- **Chapter 5 - Implementation:** This chapter gives an in-depth description of the implementation of the more interesting and/or complex features developed in the project.
- **Chapter 6 - Solution evaluation:** This chapter presents a test case to evaluate the implemented scheduling solution while also describing the tests conducted to verify the system features.
- **Chapter 7 - Conclusions:** This chapter summarizes the final product advantages and possible future improvements. Additionally, this chapter delves into the accomplishment of the project goals, stating whether the internship was a success or a failure. Finally, the chapter mentions the overall project/internship experience.

2 State of the Art

Initially, this chapter will allow the reader to understand the origin and theoretical standpoint of the project. Next, the previous project implementation is detailed, pointing its many limitations. After, a set of existing similar solutions will be presented. Finally, an analysis of architectural patterns and technologies, which can be used in the project will be carried out.

2.1 Context

In recent years, the world is transitioning towards becoming more sustainable and carbon-neutral, driven by a significant change in the environmental awareness of the population [17]–[19] and by the implementation of new green policies by organizations and governments [20], [21]. Subsequently, the adoption of renewable energy sources (RES) like wind and solar is growing at a significant rate, with the annual installed capacity growing almost 45% in 2020, in the world, the biggest increase since 1999 [22]. Moreover, as prices for installing solar panels keep dropping, households play an increasingly prominent role in this transition [1], injecting their production surplus into the grid.

The high penetration of renewable sources into power grids, especially rooftop-based solar plants, results in difficulties maintaining the necessary grid balance. As a result, over the course of the day, the grid energy demand generates a duck-shaped energy consumption curve; hence duck shape becoming the term introduced by the California Independent System Operator (CAISO) [2] to describe the increasingly problematic grid unbalance phenomenon happening in the city as more and more solar panels were being installed. Hawaii and Australia have also stated similar problems [4], [23].

Figure 2 illustrates CAISO's energy consumption curve on the 31st of March throughout the years (total energy consumption minus energy input from solar generation).

The time imbalance between peak demand and renewable energy production is problematic since conventional power plants require long periods to stop or start producing energy. Due to these prolonged lead times, grid operators cannot efficiently scale down energy production during the midday drop in demand and reinstate energy generation in time for the post-sunset peak, leading to increased operating costs [24].

In addition, at certain times of the year, namely Spring and Summer, there is also an overgeneration risk, in which grid power consumption is lower than the grid minimum power supply [25]. This problem occurs because some non-dispatchable generation sources, such as nuclear and geothermal power plants, cannot be temporarily turned off [3].

Figure 2 - Evolution of CAISO's grid energy consumption curve [26].

Overgeneration can lead to permanent damage of devices connected to the grid [27], so grid operators are forced to curtail RES or implement negative electricity prices to force demand upwards, thus reducing both environmental and economic benefits of renewable sources [5]. In light of these problems, it is crucial to develop and implement grid load balancing solutions to minimize the impact of the introduction of RES in energy systems, preserving its economic and environmental benefits.

2.2 Grid Load Balancing Solutions

This section describes energy balancing services and strategies used by grid operators to maintain system equilibrium, helping the reader to better frame and understand the Flexigy goals in the context.

2.2.1 Energy Storage Solutions

Grid energy storage is a set of large-scale solutions developed to store electricity when demand is low or when energy production is plentiful, for later returning it once demand peaks.

This section will go over some of the main energy storage techniques used by grid operators.

2.2.1.1 Pumped-storage hydroelectricity

One traditional alternative to the unbalance problem is to use excessive electricity production to pump water from a lower to a higher elevation reservoir, storing the energy under the form of gravitational potential of water. Later, this energy potential can generate electricity when energy demand exceeds the energy supply [6].

2.2.1.2 Battery storage power stations

Batteries, implemented at a large enough scale, are the fastest responding solution to help flatten the curve fluctuation and maintain the voltage profile. Companies such as Tesla and Mitsubishi [10] have implemented large-scale battery storage in Hawaii [7], Australia [8], and California [9] to compensate for the fluctuations caused by the introduction of RES in the energy grid. For the moment, the main drawback of this solution seems to be the price of installation [11].

2.2.1.3 Power-to-X

The power-to-x solution is an electricity conversion technique that uses surplus energy generation to produce a wide range of chemicals that require large amounts of energy to be transformed. For example, figure 3 shows how the power-to-hydrogen (P2H2) method uses excess energy in the water electrolysis process to generate hydrogen [28], and how later it can be used to power vehicles, households, or even in the production of synthetic chemicals [29].

Figure 3 - Power-to-Hydrogen solution [29]

2.2.1.4 Vehicle-to-Grid

The vehicle-to-grid (V2G) is a state-of-the-art solution in which battery-powered vehicles, such as plug-in hybrids (PHEV) and battery electric vehicles (BEV), act as distributed battery storage power stations providing electricity flow from the grid to the car and back [30].

Although not being a goal of this internship, Flexigy's consortium plans to implement V2G solutions in the platform.

2.2.2 Energy Demand Management

Energy Demand Management (EDM) services are a set of methods used by grid operators to achieve grid balance by manipulating and managing consumers' energy demand [31]. Section 4.2.3.3.9 focuses on this feature design.

This sub-section will describe Flexigy's required EDM services: **the interruptibility service** and the **regulating reserve** method.

2.2.2.1 Interruptibility Service

The TSO directly provides the interruptibility service to maintain energy grid balance during periods of overgeneration. In this service, grid operators establish Interruptibility Service Access Agreement (ISAA) contracts [33] with big energy consumers (industries) connected to the medium-to-high tension, which reduce their electricity consumption when requested by the grid in exchange for financial compensation [34].

The minimum interruptible power for a consumer to establish ISAA contracts in Portugal is 4MW. In 2020, REN, Portugal TSO, contracted 47 different locations responsible for 690 MW of interruptible power, summing up to more than 102 M€ of monetary compensations [35].

2.2.2.2 Regulating Reserves

Regulating Reserves are a grid solution for both under and overproduction problems [36]. This service aims to regulate the power difference instantaneously during the lead time required by large coal plants to meet the changing energy demand. At its basis, a regulation reserve request expresses an action (i.e., increase or decrease), an energy amount, and a duration. (e.g., "I need to decrease 5 kW in the next 5 minutes").

2.2.3 Energy Flexibility

This sub-section outlines the core concepts applied to describe energy flexibility, the concept at the basis of the Flexigy project, and one of the state-of-the-art solutions to the grid energy unbalance problem.

2.2.3.1 The Flex Offer concept

The Flex Offer concept is the European Union FP7 project MIRABEL [37] proposal for a standardized model representing flexible electric loads of both consumption (e.g., charging electric vehicles, heat pumps, equipment for domestic use) and production (e.g., discharging batteries, solar panels) devices. Some of the concept applications revolve around energy commercialization in an energy market and grid load balancing.

In their simplest form, Flex Offers are generic entities expressing an amount of energy, a duration, a price, the earliest start time, and the latest start time (e.g., (i) "I need 5 kWh in 3 hours between 01:00 and 05:00, for a price of 0.25 € / kWh", (ii) "I can supply between 20 and 25 kWh, between 3 pm and 6 pm, for a price of 0.35 € / kWh").

Figure 4 displays a visual representation of a Flex Offer with the earliest start time (ES) and the latest start time (LS). The energy requirements are expressed in intervals of variable length (slices). The minimum and maximum amounts of energy are additionally specified (the striped area expresses the difference between the maximum and minimum amounts).

Figure 4 - Flex Offer example [38]

A Flex Offer is an "option" that a consumer/producer introduces to a market. The Flex Offer can be rejected or accepted. If the option is accepted, the Flex Offer receives an initial schedule. In the simplest case, the scheduling is carried out as specified. Nonetheless, one of the strengths of this concept only shows when the situation does not go as planned, for example, due to a sudden drop in solar energy production. In this case, the Flex Offer can be rescheduled to when the solar is forecasted to produce more.

2.2.3.2 Flex Offer Life Cycle

As described in [39], a Flex Offer goes through several phases during its life cycle. Below, each phase of the process is presented, and some of the most important to the development of the Flexigy project are highlighted.

- I. **Data collection:** The first step towards creating a Flex Offer implies collecting and storing historical energy consumption data from devices. **Data collection** is done in the Flexigy project with the help of VPS's IoT devices and platform.
- II. **Predictive Model of Flexibility Patterns:** Flex Offers energy profiles are created essentially from future consumption and flexibility forecasts. **Forecasting methods** are one of the research subjects of this internship and will be further discussed in section 2.4.2.
- III. **Flex Offer Aggregation:** Flex Offers are combined into large, aggregated Flex Offers, more valuable to the energy market and computationally manageable.
- IV. **Flex Offer Optimization/Trading:** Flex Offers are scheduled to optimize grid energy loads or traded directly on the market. **Scheduling Flex Offers** is one of the goals of this internship, and it will be further explained in section 2.4.3.
- V. **Flex Offer Disaggregation:** Scheduled aggregated Flex Offers are sent back by the market and are separated to obtain the individual schedule for each device.
- VI. **Flex Offer Execution:** In this step, devices actuate accordingly to the Flex Offer schedule. Devices can actuate either by themselves or, with the help of external devices such as smart plugs, in cases where it cannot execute Flex Offer or integrate the Flex Offer mechanisms in its software. **Flex Offer execution** according to the Flex Offer schedule is one of the developed features in the Flexigy platform, and its design is presented in section 4.2.3.3.10.
- VII. **Flex Offer Execution Verification:** In the end, it is possible to verify the Flex Offer scheduling effectiveness by measuring the deviation between what was scheduled and what was consumed by the device.

2.2.3.3 Flexibility Types

Devices' flexibility types can be categorized according to two factors: (i) instantaneous energy consumption and (ii) usage time flexibility [40]. More specifically, three different kinds of devices are specified:

- **Fixed Devices** - Fixed devices are non-flexible devices whose energy consumption and the moment of that consumption cannot be modified (e.g., TV, lights).
- **Shiftable Devices** - Shiftable devices are flexible devices allowing only to shift the moment of energy consumption in time without modifying the load profile. (e.g., washing machine, dishwasher). These devices offer a possible solution to optimize grid load management and are crucial to the proof of concept developed in this internship.

- **Elastic devices** - Elastic devices offer the most flexibility, being fully adjustable in terms of usage time and instantaneous power consumption (e.g., heater, electric car). Similarly to shiftable devices, elastic devices provide grid load management capabilities to a greater extent.

Figure 5 - Devices' flexibility types

2.3 Previous Flexigy Implementations

The previously implemented prototype of the Flexigy project has many limitations and does not respond to the consortium goals for the platform. This section presents the developed proof of concept while describing its shortcomings.

First, the prototype architecture uses a not easily scalable and maintainable design, with tight coupling between software components and without a clear separation of concerns. Since Flexigy is a research project, it is prone to constant changes and improvements, making the proof-of-concept architecture unsuitable for needed system expansion. During the internship, a new architecture was designed and implemented, tackling the enumerated limitations.

Second, the prototype did not implement any of the EDM features required by the consortium and did not tackle the device actuations and the buildings' unpredictable consumptions features.

Third, the prototype developed a front-end platform that allowed the visualization of devices' historical consumptions. This feature connected the platform to the VPS API, fetching the device's data and showing it to the user. Figure 6 demonstrates the prototype User Interface showing a device's consumptions throughout the day.

Figure 6 – Previous prototype UI showing a device consumption [41]

Concerning the day-ahead Flex Offer scheduling, the previous project presented a prototype algorithm, but it did not implement it as the solution did not account for most of the consortium goals, constraints, and business rules. Because of this, the scheduling algorithms are totally reengineered, designed, implemented, and tested during the course of the internship.

2.4 Related Projects

This section presents projects and solutions related to the main concepts of the Flexigy system. First, a set of energy flexibility projects will be analyzed as these will help to better understand the platform core concepts. Then, a collection of Flex Offer scheduling and energy forecasting algorithms will be described as the basis to engineer similar features during the project development.

2.4.1 Energy Flexibility Related Projects

Energy management systems allowing users to plan their energy consumption by exploring their energy flexibility are a relatively recent reality, with the majority still in experimental

phases. In this section, we will describe some of the most important projects about the subject.

2.4.1.1 MIRABEL

MIRABEL (Micro Request-Based Aggregation, Forecasting and Scheduling of Energy Demand, Supply, and Distribution) [37] is an EU-funded research project aiming to develop a solution to better integrate renewable energy sources (RES) in the power grids. This system uses energy flexibility expressed by market players as the key to balance energy supply and demand. In the Mirabel system, all market players are called prosumers, as they may be producers, consumers, or both at the same time.

Renewable energy sources like wind and solar power production are highly dependent on external and uncontrollable factors, thus becoming one of the biggest challenges of this project. The Mirabel system supports the integration of non-scheduled RES better than previous proposals by implementing forecasting methodologies [37].

In figure 7, we see the energy consumption with and without the MIRABEL system. The dark grey and shaded areas delineate the non-flexible and flexible demand, respectively. The dotted line represents renewable energy production. With the help of the MIRABEL Flex Offers, the grid can be better balanced by shifting energy demand through time to match positions of larger renewable production.

Figure 7 - Balancing with and without the MIRABEL concept [37]

Moreover, figure 8 illustrates the lifecycle of Flex Offers in the Mirabel system. Following their creation and acceptance by the system, the Flex Offers are aggregated, preserving their flexibility. Afterward, the scheduling is performed based on forecasts to achieve a greater balance of the grid. After being scheduled, the Flex Offers are disaggregated and returned to

the prosumer. Once the execution is carried out, billing is conducted, and depending on the benefits of the Flex Offer for the utility company, an incentive may be provided to the prosumer [42].

Figure 8 - Flex Offer lifecycle in the MIRABEL system [37]

2.4.1.2 Total Flex

TotalFlex's goal is to develop an environmentally friendly and cost-effective flexible energy market-based system, including both flexible energy consumption and flexible energy production while considering the balance and restrictions of the grid [43].

TotalFlex implements energy flexibility by applying the Flex Offer concept proposed in the EU project MIRABEL. However, instead of each user stating their flexibility, the TotalFlex project aims towards predicting it based on historical energy usage [44].

Therefore, this project focuses on accurate flex detection and forecast, load prediction, and automatically generated Flex Offer. Flex detection and forecast refer to the detection and prediction of the available device's energy load flexibility (e.g., "An EV with a maximum charging power level of 10 kW needs 4 kWh of energy with an 8 hour time flexibility starting at 10 pm and ending at 6:00 am the next day).

2.4.1.3 GOFLEX

The Generalized Operational FLEXibility for Integrating Renewables in the Distribution Grid (GOFLEX) project is a European Union Horizon 2020 funded project created by a consortium of 12 international partners from Ireland, Slovenia, Denmark, Germany, Cyprus, and Switzerland currently being tested at three different European cities and involving over 400 prosumers from industry, smart-buildings, and public transports [45].

GOFLEX aims to implement scalable, commercially viable, and easy to deploy technology solutions that enable regional actors like Prosumers, Demand Side Operators, Energy Suppliers, Microgrid Operators, and Energy Communities to aggregate and trade distributed flexibilities in a dynamic energy market [45].

Figure 9 shows the various project participants exchanging energy flexibility with the respective Flexibility Market. The Flexibility Market then negotiates with the Distribution Observability Service entity to optimize the scheduling of the flexibilities considering the energy predictions made by the Forecasting Platform.

Figure 9 - GOFLEX system representation [39]

2.4.1.4 Universal Smart Energy Framework

The Universal Smart Energy Framework (USEF) [46] framework is based on the Flex Offers concept previously mentioned. USEF is used by several projects [47]–[50] in the energy trading market. This framework delineates a set of rules for scheduling consumptions, and it aims to accelerate and facilitate users' transition to the smart energy market, deliver business opportunities for producers/consumers, reduce congestion in electrical distribution networks and reduce consumption costs for all users [51].

In Figure 10, it is possible to verify the relationships between entities belonging to the USEF energy market model and some of the characteristics related to its use.

Figure 10 - USEF market model men [51]

In this model, all elements are represented in the same way, with no distinction between consumers and producers. After describing the flexibility of the devices associated with the consumer/producer, they are sent to an aggregator to see their flexibility optimized given the needs and possibilities presented by the virtual energy market [52].

After receiving the portfolio with energy flexibilities (Flex Offers) from the prosumer's devices, the aggregator communicates with three entities to optimize energy flexibility transactions.

- Balance Responsible Party (BRP) - In this entity, the balance between supply and demand is carried out in the portfolio of energy flexibilities since it allows communication between several aggregators [53].
- Transmission System Operator (TSO) - This entity is responsible for managing the balance of the grid at a larger scale. BRPs benefit this entity since the increase in transactions in the energy market will increase the TSOs' balance capacity. The greater the equilibrium capacity of the TSO, the higher the efficiency and economic benefits to the energy grid [54].
- Distribution System Operator (DSO) - This entity allows the consumer/producer to participate in the energy grid through the energy market [55].

2.4.1.5 DOMINOES

DOMINOES [56] is a project created by a consortium of 8 international partners, in which ISEP's R&D unit GECAD is included. The project aims to show that consumers can truly and effectively play a significant role in the distributed electricity markets by providing an easy and effective way for local energy markets to interact and exchange flexibility with market stakeholders like DSOs, aggregators, retailers, and other consumers. In addition, the project develops a set of innovative demand response, peer-to-peer trading and, grid management

services by designing, developing, and testing a scalable platform. The project will validate its solution in three validation sites:

- LUT laboratory facilities and test benches (a microgrid environment in Lappeenranta, Finland)
- CNET validation site (a distribution grid environment in Évora, Portugal)
- Virtual Power Plant validation site (an environment for VPP aggregation/balancing/demand response services, distributed across bank branches in Portugal)

2.4.2 Energy Forecasting

Given the economic and environmental importance of energy demand predictions, a set of forecasting methods, such as regression, time series, genetic algorithms, and neural networks, have been developed over the years. Predicting accurate consumption and production profiles is also essential for creating better Flex Offers and improving overall system performance. This section will focus on buildings' energy demand forecasting techniques, as this was one of the features to be developed during the internship.

The solution presented in [57] uses a dynamic multiple regression model that achieves a very good correlation coefficient of 98.7%. A multiple regression model is a statistical technique that uses several explanatory variables to predict the outcome of an objective variable [58]. The authors in [57] used the energy demand as the objective variable and the air temperature and historical consumptions as explanatory variables as inputs to a mathematical multiple regression model.

On the other hand, the authors in [59] explored the genetic algorithms as a solution to forecast the energy demand in the residential and commercial sectors. A genetic algorithm (GA) is a metaheuristic evolutionary algorithm inspired by the natural selection process. GA are commonly used to generate solutions to complex problems by using biologically inspired operators such as crossover, mutation, and selection [60].

2.4.3 Flex Offer Scheduling

The Flex Offer scheduling, first introduced by the MIRABEL project, is a non-standard and highly complex scheduling problem because of:

1. The Flex Offer structure, consisting of a start time, an end time, and several time intervals (e.g., 15-minute time intervals in the MIRABEL system), each one with its

properties substantially increases problem complexity in terms of the number of candidate solutions.

2. The Flex Offer scheduling relies on a cost minimization evaluation function that is not relative to each time interval but rather to a composed cost function.
3. The expected large number of Flex Offers to be processed in the scheduling platform raises concerns about the computing resources needed.

In the following sections, we will overview some of the presented solutions to this problem.

2.4.3.1 Randomized Greedy Search

The solution presented by [61] uses a randomized greedy search algorithm to solve the Flex Offer Scheduling Problem. Randomized greedy search algorithms are based on successive iterations of greedy randomized solutions and subsequent iterative improvements through a local optimization [62].

Algorithm 1 first creates a conditional stopping criterion (e.g., the minimum cost for the solution). Secondly, it tries to schedule all Flex Offers randomly by finding the best fit for each one (1.a.ii) and then adding the scheduled Flex Offer to the solution (1.a.iii). Finally, the randomly generated schedule is evaluated, and if its cost is less than the specified stop criterion at the start, a solution is returned. Otherwise, the algorithm will continue to schedule all Flex Offers until a solution is found. Given that this algorithm implements a greedy search algorithm, it is not guaranteed that it will find the globally optimal solution [63].

Randomized greedy search

- 1) Until the stopping criterion is met, repeat the following steps:
 - a) Repeat until all flex-offers have been scheduled:
 - i) Randomly select a flex-offer.
 - ii) Find the best schedule for this flex-offer.
 - iii) Add this schedule to the solution.
 - b) Save the best solution found so far.
- 2) Return the best solution.

Algorithm 1 - Randomized greedy search pseudocode [61]

2.4.3.2 Evolutionary Algorithm

The solution developed by [64] is based on an evolutionary algorithm that handles all Flex Offers simultaneously. Evolutionary algorithms (EAs) are optimization algorithms that start with a population of random solutions and use evolutionary principles of crossover, selection, and mutation to find better solutions [65].

Algorithm 2 starts by creating an initial population of solutions where all schedules' start times and energy amounts are chosen randomly. Then, the evolutionary algorithm is used until a stopping condition is met (e.g., the minimum cost for the solution).

Evolutionary algorithm

- 1) Create and evaluate an initial population of random solutions.
- 2) Until the stopping criterion is met, repeat the following steps:
 - a) Select two parents using tournament selection.
 - b) Cross the parents to get two offspring solutions.
 - c) For each offspring solution repeat:
 - i) Mutate and evaluate the offspring.
 - ii) Replace the worst solution of the population with the offspring, if it is better than the worst solution.
- 3) Return the best solution in the population.

Algorithm 2 - Evolutionary Algorithm pseudocode [64]

The evolutionary algorithm can explore a larger set of Flex Offers scheduling solutions than the randomized greedy search algorithm. However, it too does not guarantee the globally optimal solution [65].

2.5 Existing Technologies

This section describes and analyzes the architectural patterns, architectural representation models, back-end technologies, database technologies, and visualization platforms studied to develop the Flexigy project.

2.5.1 Architectural Patterns

Architectural patterns are reusable solutions to frequently occurring problems in software architecture within a given context [66].

This section will describe and analyze the benefits and drawbacks of two architectural patterns utilized in web development.

2.5.1.1 Layered Architecture

The Layered Architecture is the traditional method to design software architectures. This pattern structures the application into n different horizontal layers, each containing components related to the particular layer concern [67]. Although it does not specify the number of layers, most layered architectures consist of four layers [68]. Figure 11 shows the traditional layers as well as the dependencies between them.

Figure 11 - Layered Architecture Pattern [68]

The layered architecture layers are:

- **Presentation Layer** – This layer contains all the software objects and components responsible for sending the response back to the client or presenting the UI to the end-user.
- **Application Layer** - Includes all the application's business logic to fulfill its functional requirements (e.g., create, update, or delete services).
- **Domain Layer** - Represents the software underlying domain entities.
- **Infrastructure Layer** - Contains the application classes responsible for persisting data in the database, such as repositories.

The Layered Architecture main benefits are:

- **Simplicity** - The concept is straightforward to learn and implement.
- **Separation of concerns** - This architecture guarantees the separation of concerns as each layer only has a single responsibility.

The drawbacks of the Layered Architecture are:

- **No built-in scalability** - Because of the tight coupling between the layers of this architecture, applications built using it are generally challenging to scale.
- **No dependency inversion** – The Layered architectural pattern does not adopt the fifth SOLID design principle, the Dependency Inversion Principle [69]. Thus, in a traditional Layered Architecture, the dependencies are towards the concretions of the lower layers resulting in tougher system adaptability to changes.

2.5.1.2 Onion Architecture

The Onion architectural pattern, introduced by J. Palermo in 2008, aims to solve some of the traditional architectures' fundamental issues, such as tight coupling and separation of concerns, while also offering better system scalability, maintainability, and testability [70].

This architectural pattern is based on the Inversion of Control Principle, i.e., placing the domain and services layers at the application's core while externalizing the infrastructure. In this architecture, the outer layers can depend on inner layers. However, a layer must be independent of its outermost layers [71]. Figure 12 shows the concentric layered architecture, as well as the dependency direction between layers.

Figure 12 - Onion Architectural Pattern [70]

The layers of the onion architecture are, from the core to the exterior:

- **Entities Layer** - At the center of the application's architecture is the layer that contains all the domain entities. These domain entities represent the business objects and do not have dependencies on any other layer.
- **Use Cases Layer** - This layer defines all the services related to the application business logic, depending directly on the inner domain layer. Additionally, it specifies system interfaces that serve as a contract to the implementation of outermost layers (e.g., repository interfaces used by the infrastructure layer).
- **Interface Adapters** - This layer is the bridge between the external infrastructure and the domain layers. The elements of this layer (e.g., controllers, repositories, or API adapters implementations) do not directly depend on the inner layer implementations but instead on the interface contracts defined by it.
- **Frameworks and Drivers Layer** - The outer onion ring is for frequently changing components, such as the Databases, UI, tests, and messaging systems.

The onion architecture main benefits are:

- Application architecture is built on top of a domain model.
- Database access and service calls are external to the domain architecture and easily interchangeable.
- Flexible, sustainable, and portable architecture.
- Easily and quickly testable as the application core does not depend on anything.
- Onion architecture ensures flexibility, sustainability, portability, and maintainability.

The only major disadvantages of this architectural pattern are its big learning curve and setup time.

Given the benefits of the onion architecture when compared to the layered architecture and since one has already developed a solution using it, this architecture was picked for the Flexigy platform (section 4.2).

2.5.2 Architectural Representation

Documenting and efficiently communicating software design is critical for project development and improvement. The architectural design should be easily and effectively communicated to all team members, business owners, stakeholders, and other interested parties [72]. This section summarizes some well-known methods for describing system architectures.

2.5.2.1 UML

The Unified Modelling Language (UML) is a general-purpose modeling language created to standardize the different notational approaches used at the time. The language specifies a set of diagrams to help software developers analyze, document, and communicate the system artifacts [73]. Some of the diagrams specified by the UML are:

- Class Diagram - This diagram describes object types in the system and their relationships (e.g., Association, Inheritance, Aggregation).
- Use Case Diagrams – It models the system's functional requirements in terms of use cases.
- Component Diagrams – It depicts how system components are connected to form larger components or software systems.
- Sequence Diagrams – This diagram illustrates objects interactions over time in a particular use case.

2.5.2.2 4+1 View Model

The 4+1 View Model is an information organization framework introduced by P. Kruchten [74] to facilitate the description of complex systems to various stakeholders. The 4+1 View Model proposes the use of the following five views, each one addressing a specific set of concerns:

- Logical View: Describes the system design and components.
- Process View: Illustrates the dynamic aspects of the design, capturing their concurrency and synchronization aspects.
- Physical View: Maps the different software components onto the hardware as well as the connection between these components.
- Implementation View: This view is concerned with the organization of the software in its development environment.
- Scenarios View: The "plus one" view is directed to the user's point of view as it describes the system functionalities and capabilities with a few selected use cases.

Figure 13 shows a visual representation of the 4+1 View Model and the connections between the different views.

Figure 13 - 4+1 Model

The 4+1 Model's major disadvantage is that it does not specify the detail level that should be used in the diagrams [74].

2.5.2.3 C4 Model

The C4 Model is an abstraction-first approach created by S. Brown [75] to help software architects and developers to describe and document software architecture at different levels of detail. The author compares this model to the zoom feature used in google maps (figure 14), as a user can gradually "zoom in" between the high-level diagram representation (e.g., general view of the world on the map) and the lower-level, more concrete views (e.g., street view in a map).

The model presents a set of four hierarchical levels:

- Context (Level 1): The highest level of abstraction shows how the software system relates with users and other systems.
- Container (Level 2): Decomposition the system into interrelated containers, showing how they communicate with finer detail.
- Components (Level 3): Zoom in to each container, illustrating a set of interrelated components that integrate it.
- Code (Level 4): Zoom into an individual component to describe how it was implemented.

Figure 14 – C4 detail levels

Nevertheless, the C4 Model has a major disadvantage, as it does not adopt the UML notation [76].

2.5.2.4 Combining the 4+1 View Model with the C4 Model

The models mentioned above can be combined to achieve greater architecture explainability by applying the 4+1 View Model framework for each abstraction level of the C4 Model [77].

Figure 15 illustrates the different diagram possibilities using both models.

Figure 15 - C4 Model and 4+1 Model combination

In the design of the Flexigy project (section 4.2), the combination of both the C4 and the 4+1 models will be used.

2.5.3 Back-End Technologies

This section will present two of the most widely used back-end technologies: Node.js and the .NET Core. Both represent the state-of-the-art for this technology, have a lot of documentation, and an active community.

2.5.3.1 NodeJs

Node.js [78] is a modular, free-to-use JavaScript interpreter that allows the development of asynchronous event-oriented multiplatform applications. Node.js modules are obtained through the Node Package Manager (NPM) by downloading and adding reusable packages to the application. Because of its asynchronous event-oriented architecture, Node.js is the advisable solution when building scalable systems such as I/O bound applications, data streaming applications, and data-intensive real-time applications.

2.5.3.2 .Net Core

The .NET Core is a free, general-purpose, open-source, and cross-platform framework maintained by Microsoft that runs on Windows, macOS, and Linux operating systems.

This framework is oriented towards a fast and easy development of different applications such as web applications, IoT, mobile, and microservices. The architecture of this technology is also built for unit testing, dependency injection, and asynchronous programming [79].

The .NET Core is modular and only includes by default core features to run basic .NET apps. Other modules and features are provided through the NuGet packages, which can be added to the application as needed [80].

The .Net Core was the chosen back-end technology for the Flexigy platform because the consortium systems, where the platform aims to be integrated in the future, use .Net Core.

2.5.4 Database Technologies

The following database typologies were considered for the system database development: (i) Relational databases; (ii) Non-relational databases.

In a relational database, data is stored in tables and related to each other. In contrast, in a database non-relational database, data is saved in documents without any relationship between the tables [81].

This section outlines two database technologies: SQL Server (relational database) and MongoDB (non-relational database). These two technologies were chosen as there was prior knowledge of both.

2.5.4.1 SQL Server

Microsoft SQL Server [82], developed by Microsoft, is a database management system (DBMS) that allows the persistence of information in a relational way, that is, in tables. In these tables, each column represents an entity's attribute, and each line represents a persisted object. It is possible to perform searches on this system using the SQL Query language.

2.5.4.2 Mongo DB

MongoDB [83], developed by MongoDB.inc, is a database software that allows the persistence of information in documents, that is, in a non-relational way. In these documents, the information is persisted in JSON format through "key-value" pairs. It is possible to perform searches on this system using the JSON Queries.

2.5.5 Data Visualization Technologies

This section describes four different data visualization techniques. The first, Angular, was chosen because it is widely used to develop front-end solutions and because of previous knowledge in the technology. Moreover, data visualization technologies will be presented as they allow faster development of a platform to check the system time-series data.

2.5.5.1 Angular

Angular [84] is a cross-platform front-end solution that allows the development of web applications in Typescript language. This tool is modular, and only the modules necessary for its operation are integrated into the application. Angular automatically optimizes the performance of applications created on this platform.

2.5.5.2 Kibana

Kibana [85] is an open-source visualization and exploration platform used for logs and data. This tool offers easy application monitoring and operational intelligence capabilities through features like histograms, line graphs, pie charts, heat maps, and built-in geospatial support.

2.5.5.3 Power BI

Power BI is a business analytics cloud platform provided by Microsoft as part of the Microsoft Power Platform. It aims to provide an easy-to-use interface for end-users to create their own dashboards and reports. In addition, this service also provides business intelligence, data preparation, and data discovery capabilities [86].

2.5.5.4 Grafana

Grafana [87] is an open-source dashboard data visualization tool focused on providing ways to visualize time series data through graphics. It offers a pluggable panel architecture in which different plugins can be installed to provide new data sources.

Given the limited time to develop and implement the Flexigy platform during this internship, we have decided to use an already built data visualization platform, thus excluding React. From the other described solutions, Grafana was the selected tool due to its easy integration capabilities and time-series focus.

2.6 Chapter summary

This chapter explored the project problem context, introducing its implications to the energy grid and population in general. Then, a collection of traditional solutions to the energy unbalance problem was analyzed, highlighting those related to the project goals.

Second, the Flex Offer concept was presented, delineating its most essential features and qualities. Afterward, the Flexigy previous proof of concept implementation was described. Next, a set of related projects and solutions were described, leading to a better understating of the domain challenges.

Finally, architectural patterns and technologies were studied and compared for later project implementation.

3 Requirements Engineering and Analysis

This chapter describes the project's requirements and business model analysis.

3.1 Requirements Engineering

Software requirements are descriptions of features, services, and constraints applied to the requested software that should aim to deliver the user's expectations for the final product. Some requirements are obvious, expected, or well outlined by the client, while others can be hidden, unknown, or unexpected from the client's perspective [88].

The process of gathering, defining and, documenting these software requirements from the client is known as requirements engineering [89].

In the following sub-chapters, the captured functional and non-functional requirements will be addressed.

3.1.1 Functional Requirements

Functional requirements (FR) specify basic functionalities that a system or its components must be able to perform [90].

In combination with the project consortium and after analyzing the project goals, the following functional requirements were outlined:

- FR 1. The system should be able to handle multiple users and devices.
- FR 2. The system should be able to register users.
 - a. When filling out a form to register a user, the unregistered user must specify:
 - i. Username;
 - ii. Password;
 - iii. Buyer Profile;
 - iv. Supplier Profile.
- FR 3. The system should allow users to add devices to their accounts.
 - a. When filling out a form to register a device, the user must specify:
 - i. Device tag (number tag identifying the device in VPS's platform);
 - ii. Name;
 - iii. Device Type (i.e., solar panel, wet-device, fridge, other);
 - iv. Maximum minutes the device can be turned off.
- FR 4. The system should be able to get device energy measurements.
- FR 5. The system should allow the user to create a Flex Offer manually.

- FR 6. The system should allow the user to create a Flex Offer, automatically forecasting its energy profile.
- FR 7. The system should be able to optimize community energy consumption through the scheduling of users' Flex Offers and according to the following restraints:
- a. It is always more advantageous for the prosumer to consume the maximum amount of self-produced energy.
 - b. The energy will be injected into the grid; however, it will not be sold to the grid but to the Community Virtual Energy Pool (VEP). In the community, consumers and prosumers will purchase energy in an automated manner.
 - c. There will always be times when the PV energy produced by the community is not enough. In this case, the platform will buy energy from large producers.
 - d. The optimization should be performed according to the users' buyer and supplier profiles.
 - i. Buyer Profiles:
 1. **Bold** – Maximize renewable energy consumption regardless of price.
 2. **Cautious** – Minimize energy cost.
 3. **Local Community Supporter** – Maximize community energy consumption.
 - ii. Supplier Profiles:
 1. **Go-Ahead** – Sells all electricity production.
 2. **Tactical** – Sell only the surplus of self-production.
- FR 8. The system should handle EDM requests from the TSO to either reduce or increase energy consumption. The consortium imposed the following constraint:
- a. Whenever there is an EDM request from the TSO, the platform must prioritize this service. Therefore, the scheduling optimization of flexible offers can be interrupted.
- FR 9. The system should be able to control devices based on the Flex Offers scheduling.
- FR 10. The system should show the Flex Offers' energy profile.
- FR 11. The system should show the Flex Offers' schedule.
- FR 12. The system should show Users' energy production profiles.
- FR 13. The system should be able to show energy prices.

3.1.2 Non-Functional Requirements

Non-functional requirements (NFR) define implicit or expected quality attributes, constraints, and restrictions of a software system [91]. The main non-functional requirements of the Flexigy project are as follows:

3.1.2.1 Performance and Scalability

Performance pertains to how well a computer system or software responds to interactions under particular workloads [92]. Scalability assesses the highest workloads under which the system will still meet performance requirements [93].

Since the project goal is to be installed in energy communities with hundreds of users, handling and scheduling large amounts of data, certain precautions regarding the system performance and scalability must be taken.

NFR 1. All queries to VPS API should be reduced to the strictly necessary and or even completely removed when used for each list element.

NFR 2. System components must be simply swappable for other most performing ones.

NFR 3. The scheduling algorithms should not require large amounts of computing power to run.

3.1.2.2 Portability

Portability defines how systems can be used or launched in different environments [94].

The portability of this platform must be ensured as the consortium should be able to implement, test, or use the system in the future.

NFR 4. The Flexigy platform must be easily installed and run in any OS.

3.1.2.3 Maintainability

Maintainability is related to the ease with which a software component can be modified to correct errors, improve existing features, or adapt to a changing environment [95].

As a research project, the Flexigy system is prone to continuous changes in implemented features, so it is essential to define requirements about its maintainability.

NFR 5. Continuous platform evolution and change must be considered when developing the system architecture.

3.1.2.4 Usability

Usability is how specific users can utilize software to achieve quantified objectives with effectiveness, efficiency, and satisfaction [96].

NFR 6. This project visualization platform must have an intuitive and appealing interface, using responsive layouts, to guarantee the adequate and helpful presentation of information regarding the Flex Offer schedule.

3.2 Analysis

Domain Analysis is how a software engineer learns, identifies, captures, and organizes information to better understand the field of business in which clients will use the software [97]. The domain model, one of the artifacts produced by the domain analysis, is a conceptual modulation of real-world concepts that incorporates behavior, data, rules, and logic [98].

With the previous domain model and the functional use cases as a basis, we developed a new domain model that captures the envisioned system. Since the enhancements made to the domain model are essential to understand the proposed solution, a domain analysis was made, and the resulting changes are documented below.

3.2.1 Domain Model

As a starting point for the analysis, the previous implementation domain model is displayed in figure 16. This will allow us to compare it with the new requirements and determine what can be maintained, what must be updated, and what needs to be added. Later, in figure 17, the new domain model will be exhibited along with a detailed description of every object.

Figure 16 - Previous project's domain model [41]

3.2.1.1 What can be kept

The previous domain model provided a good basis for the development of this project. The Flex Offer, Flex Offer Type, User, Device, and Device Type classes can be reused conceptually in the domain model since they follow the established requirements.

3.2.1.2 What must change

First, the Flex Offer scheduling process must be adapted to represent the requirements of the consortium. The Aggregator concept illustrated in Fig 15 will be replaced by the Scheduler Service, as the new implementation does not focus on aggregating Flex Offers but on optimizing the Flex Offer schedule.

Second, in the previous implementation of the project, User's profiles were not considered. Given that one of the project's requirements specifies that each Flexigy User should be prompted to select a profile for both buying and selling energy flexibility, the domain model must be changed to accommodate these features.

Third, the production and consumption values associated with Devices in the previous domain model were collapsed to the Measurement class. We applied the change because the energy values read by sensors are conceptually identical, as both identify an energy amount and a date-time.

Lastly, the energy profile concept was modified. Previously associated with devices, this class is now directly related to Flex Offers, as it may change between two different Flex Offers applied to the same device. For example, the energy profile stating the energy production of a PV installation changes according to a set of external factors between two different Flex Offers, proving that this variable class cannot be directly stored and related to a Device in a one-to-one relationship.

3.2.1.3 What needs to be added

As one of the new requirements for the Flexigy project is to handle energy demand management requests (FR8), the corresponding domain class and concepts must be integrated into the Domain Model.

Furthermore, since one of the requirements stipulates that the platform should be able to actuate over Devices (FR9), the Actuation and Actuation Schedule classes were introduced.

Moreover, because a project requirement specifies the implementation of a building energy forecast algorithm, the Forecast conceptual class was introduced in order to illustrate the value and relations of energy predictions to the different parts of the system.

3.2.1.4 New Domain Model

Figure 17 shows the Flexigy new domain model, representing all the identified business rules, relations, and constraints.

Figure 17 - Project's new domain model

Next, all the domain model entities are further detailed.

User

The User class represents the role of a client in the Flexigy system. A User has a username, a password, a list of associated devices, and both a buyer and supplier profile.

Buyer Profile

The Buyer Profile class identifies the approach chosen by the user to buy energy from the market. The buyer profile type can be either Bold, Cautious, or Community Supporter.

Supplier Profile

The Supplier Profile class depicts the preference of the user when selling produced energy to the local market. The Supplier profile type can be either Go-Ahead or Tactical.

Device

A Device belongs to a User and has a tag, a name, a Device Type, a list of Flex Offers, an actuation schedule, and a list of energy Measurements.

Device Type

The Device Type class identifies what kind of device a Device is: either a refrigerator, a wet device, a light bulb, an electric vehicle, among others.

Measurement

The measurement class is used to represent energy Measurements obtained from a Device. It has two attributes: the measurement date and the measurement value.

Flex Offer

The Flex Offer class represents the device's energy flexibility. This class has a start and end date-time for flexibility, a name to be easily identified, a Flex Offer Type, an Energy Profile, and a Schedule. Until the Scheduler generates Schedules, the Flex Offer does not have a Schedule.

Flex Offer Type

The Flex Offer class identifies the Flex Offer energy flexibility type. This type can either be fixed, shiftable, or elastic.

Flex Offer Energy Profile

The Flex Offer Energy Profile class serves as a structure to store the minimum and maximum energy consumption needed for each time slice. The energy profile can either be manually created by the User or automatically forecasted by an Energy Forecast Service.

Energy Forecast Service

The Energy Forecast Service depicts the service that predicts future energy consumptions based on historical Device Measurements.

Flex Offer Schedule

The Flex Offer Schedule class represents the plan generated by the Scheduler Service for the Flex Offer electricity consumption.

Scheduler Service

The Scheduler Service is a conceptual class created to represent a process done by an energy optimizing algorithm that schedules Flex Offers based on the users' profiles. This service recurs to both the Energy Forecast Service to predict energy production and the Virtual Energy Market to obtain electricity prices.

TSO

The TSO is a conceptual class depicting the role of a system operator in the Flexigy system. It provides electricity prices to the Scheduler and requests EDM services to the Flexigy platform.

EDM

The EDM is a conceptual representation of the TSO's interruptibility and regulating reserve requests to the system. The actuations created to respond to the TSO request originate one or more Actuation Schedules. If needed to respond to TSO requests, an EDM might reschedule Flex Offers Schedules too.

Actuation Schedule

The Actuation Schedule is a class created from either the Flex Offer Schedule or the EDM, and it serves as a structure to store a list of Actuators for a given Device.

Actuation

The Actuation class serves as a structure to store the time and action of turning on and off a Device.

3.3 Chapter summary

This chapter started by outlining the project's functional and non-functional requirements. Then an analysis of the business rules and constraints was conducted, leading to the improvement of the older domain model.

4 Design

Software design is a mechanism used to transform user requirements into more specific and detailed software terms [99]. This chapter outlines design decisions, the DDD Domain Model, and the Flexigy system's architectural design.

4.1 Data Structure

After carefully analyzing the project requirements and modulating its conceptual domain model, the concepts must be translated into a software data model using a Domain-Driven Design (DDD) approach. In DDD, the domain concepts in the analysis model are translated into software classes, constraints are identified, and interfaces are designed, resulting in a model for the solution domain [61]. In order to transform the Domain model into the system data structure, some modifications had to be done without breaking any of the defined domain rules or constraints.

First, all the conceptual classes represented in the domain model were discarded, as they are not relevant as software classes to the solution implementation.

Second, the Flex Offer scheduling representation was changed. In the new DDD Domain model, the *scheduledFlexOffer* class stores the schedule for one Flex Offer under the form of a list of *TimeSlices*. Each time slice has an hour and a list of *SourceEnergySlices*, each with its own price, energy value, and supplier type (i.e., grid, community, self-consumption). The *productionProfile* class was also introduced to facilitate the runtime handling of the grid prices for each time slice.

Third, in the case of the Flex Offers, it was decided to separate the concept of a consumption Flex Offer from the concept of a production Flex Offer because this last was always from a Fixed type.

Figure 18 shows the final version of the DDD Domain model for the Flexigy system.

Visão do Padrão Standard (1180531 (gestão do Superior de Engenharia do Porto))

Figure 18 – DDD Domain Model

4.2 Architectural Design

This sub-chapter will describe the system architecture design decisions by applying the combination of the C4 Model and the 4+1 Model as presented in the state-of-the-art section 2.4.2.

4.2.1 Level 1

This section documents the system's bigger picture, namely, its components in the Logical View and the system use cases in the Scenarios view.

4.2.1.1 Logical View

The Level 1 Logical View in figure 19 shows an overview of the developed system architecture and components.

Figure 19 - Level 1 Logical View

The system parts illustrated in the Level 1 Logical View are:

- **Flexigy System** – This component is where all the data processing, Flex Offer scheduling, and other system features are implemented. The Flexigy System component consumes three APIs and delivers two.
- **EDM API** - Provides a connection endpoint where TSO operators can request EDM services.
- **UI User** – Delivers a graphical User interface to the End User.
- **Price API** – Price API is the source of electricity prices for the system.
- **Devices API** - Devices API is where the system will connect to fetch (i) historical data, (ii) instant consumptions, and (iii) actuate on the devices.
- **Solar Forecast API** - API used by the system to forecast solar panel production.

4.2.1.2 Scenarios View

As previously mentioned in 2.4.2, the Scenarios View describes the software architecture functionalities by illustrating a set of use cases. A use case is a list of steps usually describing the interactions between a role (known in UML as an Actor) and software [97].

Given the specified functional requirements (section 3.1.1), the following system use cases were established:

Figure 20 - Use Cases for the Flexigy Project

4.2.2 Level 2

Level 2 details the system design by further decomposing it into interrelated containers and explicitly describing the system implementation packages and processes.

4.2.2.1 Logical View

The Level 2 Logical View, figure 21, zooms into the Flexigy System component illustrated in the Level 1 Logical View, showing with finer detail what containers compose the designed solution.

Figure 21 - Level 2 Logical View

The containers of the Level 2 architecture are:

- **MDF** – The Master Data Flexigy is the system container responsible for managing the domain information, such as creating and updating Users, Devices, and Flex Offers.
- **Scheduler** – This container depicts the system module developed to optimize and schedule Day-Ahead Flex Offers. This component uses the Price API to fetch electricity prices and the Energy Forecaster API to forecast both building unpredictable consumptions and energy production values.
- **Energy Forecaster** – This container represents the Flexigy module where energy consumption and production predictions are made. It relies on the Device API to fetch devices' historical data and on the Solar Forecast API to predict PV production.

- **Actuator** – Manages devices according to their schedule. It relies on the Device API to power On and Off the devices and on the MDF to obtain scheduling information.
- **EDM** – System service to handle interruptibility and regulating reserve requests. It provides an EDM API to where TSO's can make these requests. In addition, the container relies on the Device API to fetch instantaneous device consumptions and on the MDF API to update system information.
- **UI** – Container responsible for implementing system visualization.

4.2.2.2 Implementation View

The Level 2 Implementation View illustrates the package distribution of the Flexigy platform. In figure 22, we can see the six project packages and their corresponding dependencies.

Figure 22 – Level 2 Implementation View

Furthermore, figure 23 shows the mapping between the two Level 2 Views, illustrating how each package in the Implementation View correlates to each component in the Logical View.

Figure 23 - Level 2 Implementation View vs Logical View

4.2.2.3 Process View

The Level 2 Process View shows each system Use Case by using the UML sequence diagram notation. In addition, the following sections will specify each use case description, actor, pre and post conditions, the necessary data, and alternate flows.

4.2.2.3.1 UC1 - Register User

Table 1 - Use Case 1: Register User

Use Case 1: Register User	
<i>Description</i>	The unregistered user intends to register him/herself in the system so that he/she can use the platform.
<i>Actor(s)</i>	Unregistered User
<i>Preconditions</i>	1. Have access to the Flexigy system
<i>Postconditions</i>	1. The user is registered in the system and allowed to use the platform.
<i>Necessary data</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Username • Password • Buyer Profile • Supplier Profile
<i>Alternate flows</i>	The system informs the user of an error if the entered data is invalid (e.g., unknown buyer or supplier profile)

Base Flow of Events

Figure 24 - SSD UC1: Register User

4.2.2.3.2 UC2 - Create Device

Table 2 – Use Case 2: Create Device

Use Case 2: Create Device	
<i>Description</i>	The user intends to create a device.
<i>Actor(s)</i>	Flexigy User
<i>Preconditions</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Have access to the Flexigy system. 2. The device tag must be registered in VPS's platform.
<i>Postconditions</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The device is registered in the Flexigy system.
<i>Necessary data</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tag (VPS identification of the device) • Name • Device Type • Maximum Minutes Turned Off
<i>Alternate flows</i>	The system informs the user of an error if the entered data is invalid (e.g., invalid tag, inexistent device type)

Base Flow of Events

Figure 25 - SSD UC2: Create Device

4.2.2.3.3 UC3 – Get Device Measurements

Table 3 – Use Case 3: Get Device Measurements

Use Case 3: Get Device Measurements

<i>Description</i>	The user intends to obtain device measurements.
<i>Actor(s)</i>	Flexigy User
<i>Preconditions</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Have access to the Flexigy system. 2. The device must be registered in the system. 3. VPS API must have historical data of the device.
<i>Postconditions</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The measurements are obtained successfully.
<i>Necessary data</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Device Tag • Start Date-Time • Start End-Time
<i>Alternate flows</i>	<p>The system informs the user of an error if:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The entered data is invalid (e.g., inexistent device, end date before start date) • There are problems communicating with VPS's API

Base Flow of Events

Figure 26 - SSD UC3: Get Device Measurements

4.2.2.3.4 UC4 – Manually Create Flex Offer

Table 4 - Use Case 4: Manually Create Flex Offer

Use Case 4: Manually Create Flex Offer

<i>Description</i>	The user intends to manually create a device Flex Offer.
<i>Actor(s)</i>	Flexigy User
<i>Preconditions</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Have access to the Flexigy system. 2. The device must be registered in the system.
<i>Postconditions</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The Flex Offer is registered in the system.
<i>Necessary data</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Device Tag • Flexibility Start Date-Time • Flexibility Start End-Time • Flex Offer Type • Energy Profile
<i>Alternate flows</i>	The system informs the user of an error if the entered data is invalid (e.g., invalid energy profile, non-existent device, end date before start date)

Base Flow of Events

Figure 27 - SSD UC4: Manually Create Flex Offer

4.2.2.3.5 UC5 – Automatically Create Flex Offer

Table 5 - Use Case 5: Automatically Create Flex Offer

Use Case 5: Automatically Create Flex Offer

<i>Description</i>	The user intends to create a device Flex Offer by automatically forecasting its energy profile.
<i>Actor(s)</i>	Flexigy User
<i>Preconditions</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Have access to the Flexigy system. 2. The device must be registered in the system.
<i>Postconditions</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The Flex Offer is registered in the system.
<i>Necessary data</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Device Tag • Flexibility Start Date-Time • Flexibility Start End-Time • Flex Offer Type
<i>Alternate flows</i>	<p>The system informs the user of an error if:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The entered data is invalid (e.g., non-existent device, end date before start date) • There was a problem forecasting the device energy profile (UC5a).

Base Flow of Events

Figure 28 - SSD UC5: Automatically Create Flex Offer

4.2.2.3.6 UC5a – Forecast Device Energy Profile

Table 6 - Use Case 5a: Forecast Device Energy Profile

Use Case 5a: Forecast Device Energy Profile

<i>Description</i>	The user intends to predict the energy profile of a given device.
<i>Actor(s)</i>	Flexigy User
<i>Preconditions</i>	1. VPS API must have historical data of the device.
<i>Postconditions</i>	1. The device energy profile is forecasted successfully.
<i>Necessary data</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Device Tag • Start Date-Time • Start End-Time
<i>Alternate flows</i>	<p>The system informs the user of an error if:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The entered data is invalid (e.g., non-existent device, end date before start date) • There are problems communicating with the API • There is no historical data for the selected device

Base Flow of Events

Figure 29 - SSD UC5a: Forecast Device Energy Profile

4.2.2.3.7 UC6 – Schedule Day-Ahead Flex Offers

Table 7 - Use Case 6: Schedule Day-Ahead Flex Offers

Use Case 6: Schedule Day-Ahead Flex Offers

<i>Description</i>	Periodically schedule day-ahead Flex Offers.
<i>Actor(s)</i>	System Timer
<i>Frequency of Occurrence</i>	Once every day (at 10:30PM)
<i>Preconditions</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. There must be Flex Offers created for the next day. 2. Energy prices must be available for the day ahead.
<i>Postconditions</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The Flex Offers are scheduled successfully. 2. The Flex Offers schedule is saved.
<i>Alternate flows</i>	<p>The system informs the user of an error if:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There was a problem forecasting the building consumption.

Base Flow of Events

Figure 30 - SSD UC6: Schedule Day-Ahead Flex Offers

4.2.2.3.8 UC6a – Forecast building unpredictable energy consumption

Table 8 - Use Case 6a: Forecast building unpredictable energy consumption

Use Case 6a: Forecast building unpredictable energy consumption

<i>Description</i>	The user intends to forecast the building's unpredictable energy consumption profile.
<i>Actor(s)</i>	Flexigy User
<i>Preconditions</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The device must be registered in the system. 2. VPS API must have historical data of the device.
<i>Postconditions</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The energy consumption is successfully forecasted.
<i>Necessary data</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Device Tag • Date
<i>Alternate flows</i>	<p>The system informs the user of an error if:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The entered data is invalid (e.g., inexistent device, invalid date) • There are problems communicating with the VPS API • There is no historical data for the selected device

Base Flow of Events

Figure 31 - SSD UC6a: Forecast building unpredictable energy consumption

4.2.2.3.9 UC7 – Make EDM Requests

Table 9 - Use Case 7: Make EDM Requests

Use Case 7: Make EDM Requests

<i>Description</i>	The TSO wants to make EDM requests (interruptibility and regulating reserve services) to the Flexigy system.
<i>Actor(s)</i>	TSO
<i>Postconditions</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The EDM request is successfully fulfilled. 2. The device’s actuation schedule is saved.
<i>Necessary data</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Action (Increase or Decrease) • Energy Amount (in kWh) • Time (minutes)
<i>Alternate flows</i>	<p>The system informs the TSO of an error if:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The entered data is invalid (e.g., unknown action, invalid energy amount, or invalid time) • The request could not be fulfilled

Base Flow of Events

Figure 32 - SSD UC7: Make EDM Requests

4.2.2.3.10 UC8 - Create daily actuation schedule

Table 10 - Use Case 8: Create Daily Actuation Schedule

Use Case 8: Create Daily Actuation Schedule

<i>Description</i>	Create a device actuation schedule based on the scheduled Flex Offers.
<i>Actor(s)</i>	System Timer
<i>Frequency of Occurrence</i>	Once every day (at 11:30PM)
<i>Preconditions</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> There must be scheduled Flex Offers in the day ahead.
<i>Postconditions</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> The devices' actuation schedule is successfully created.
<i>Necessary data</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Start Date-Time End Date-Time
<i>Alternate flows</i>	<p>An error occurs when:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The entered data is invalid (e.g., end date before start date)

Base Flow of Events

Figure 33 - SSD UC8: Create Daily Actuation Schedule

4.2.2.3.11 UC9 – Perform Scheduled Device Actuations

Table 11 - Use Case 9: Perform Scheduled Device Actuations

Use Case 9: Perform Scheduled Device Actuations

<i>Description</i>	Turn devices On and Off according to their actuation schedule.
<i>Actor(s)</i>	System Timer
<i>Frequency of Occurrence</i>	Once every minute
<i>Preconditions</i>	1. The system must have actuation schedules.
<i>Postconditions</i>	1. The device is turned On/Off.
<i>Necessary data</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Actuation Schedule
<i>Alternate flows</i>	<p>An error occurs when:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> There are problems communicating with VPS's API

Base Flow of Events

Figure 34 - SSD UC9: Perform Scheduled Device Actuations

4.2.2.3.12 UC10 - Show Flex-Offer Energy Profile

Table 12 - Use Case 10: Show Flex-Offer Energy Profile

Use Case 10: Show Flex Offer Energy Profile

<i>Description</i>	The user intends to see the energy profile of the Flex Offers.
<i>Actor(s)</i>	Flexigy User
<i>Preconditions</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Have access to the Flexigy data visualization system. 2. The device must be registered in the system. 3. The device must have Flex Offers.
<i>Postconditions</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The device energy profile is showed successfully.
<i>Necessary data</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Device Tag • Start Date-Time • Start End-Time
<i>Alternate flows</i>	<p>The system informs the user of an error if:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The entered data is invalid (e.g., inexistent device, end date before start date) • There are no Flex Offers for the selected device

Base Flow of Events

Figure 35 - SSD UC10: Show Flex Offer Energy Profile

4.2.2.3.13 UC11 - Show Flex Offer Schedule

Table 13 - Use Case 11: Show Flex Offer Schedule

Use Case 11: Show Flex Offer Schedule

<i>Description</i>	The user intends to see the device’s Flex Offers schedule.
<i>Actor(s)</i>	Flexigy User
<i>Preconditions</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Have access to the Flexigy data visualization system. 2. The device must be registered in the system. 3. The device must have Flex Offers. 4. The Flex Offers must be scheduled.
<i>Postconditions</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The Flex Offer schedule is showed successfully.
<i>Necessary data</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Device Tag • Start Date-Time • Start End-Time
<i>Alternate flows</i>	<p>The system informs the user of an error if:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The entered data is invalid (e.g., inexistent device, end date before start date) • There are no Flex Offers for the selected device and date interval. • There is no Flex Offer schedule for the selected device and date interval.

Base Flow of Events

Figure 36 - SSD UC11: Show Flex Offer Schedule

4.2.2.3.14 UC12 - Show User Energy Production Profile

Table 14 - Use Case 12: Show User Energy Production Profile

Use Case 12: Show User Energy Production Profile

<i>Description</i>	The user intends to see his/her energy production profile.
<i>Actor(s)</i>	Flexigy User
<i>Preconditions</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Have access to the Flexigy data visualization system. 2. The device must be registered in the system.
<i>Postconditions</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The energy production is showed successfully.
<i>Necessary data</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Device Tag • Start Date-Time • Start End-Time
<i>Alternate flows</i>	<p>The system informs the user of an error if:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The entered data is invalid (e.g., inexistent device, consumption device, end date before start date)

Base Flow of Events

Figure 37 - SSD UC12: Show User Energy Production Profile

4.2.2.3.15 UC13 – Check Energy Prices

Table 15 - Use Case 13: Check Energy Prices

Use Case 13: Check Energy Prices

<i>Description</i>	The user intends to check energy prices.
<i>Actor(s)</i>	Flexigy User
<i>Preconditions</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Have access to the Flexigy data visualization system.
<i>Postconditions</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The energy prices are showed successfully.
<i>Necessary data</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Start Date-Time • End Date-Time
<i>Alternate flows</i>	<p>The system informs the user of an error if:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The entered data is invalid (e.g., end date before start date) • There was a problem communicating with the prices' data source. • There are no energy prices for the selected date interval.

Base Flow of Events

Figure 38 - SSD UC13: Check Energy Prices

4.2.3 Level 3

This section will describe the Level 3 zoom-in to each container, illustrating a set of interrelated components that integrate it in the Logical View, the correspondent packages in the Implementation View, and the use case processes in the Process View.

4.2.3.1 Logical View

Aiming to fulfill the platform's non-functional requirements, we have decided to architect system components based on the Onion Architectural pattern. As analyzed in 2.4.1, this architecture provides, among others, significant maintainability, portability, and scalability benefits when compared with a layered architecture, thus one can answer the system's NFR 2 and 5.

Figure 39 shows the design of the system components in a model composed of four concentric layers, each complying with the Onion architectural pattern.

Figure 39 - Level 3 Logical View

The system layers are, from top to bottom, or in the case of the onion architecture, from outwards to inwards:

- **Frameworks and Drivers Layer** - Contains the application routing and the Persistence components. For example, the chosen system database will be part of this layer. This layer corresponds to the outer layer of the concentric Onion Architecture.

- **Interface Adapters Layer** – System controllers, repositories, and adapters are implemented in this layer, obeying the interfaces defined by the inner Application Business Rules layer. It corresponds to the layer with the same name in the Onion Architecture.
- **Application Business Rules Layer** - Orchestrates the flow of use cases between the outermost and innermost parts of the architecture by implementing system services. Additionally, this layer specifies the interfaces that the repositories and adapters must adopt. This layer corresponds to the Use Cases layer of the Onion Architecture.
- **Model Layer** – This is the core of the application architecture and contains all the domain entities corresponding to the Entities layer of the Onion Architecture.

In addition to the implementation of the Onion Architecture, two more software patterns were used.

- The Data Transfer Object (DTO) pattern was applied between the Controller and Application Services as a way to transmit data without exposing implementation details of domain objects, thus reducing the application security risks [100].
- The Data Mapper pattern was used as an interface to create domain objects directly from DTO objects, and vice-versa aiming to keep the two application and model layers independent from one another [101].

4.2.3.2 Implementation View

The Level 3 Implementation View, figure 40, shows a more detailed approach to how the system architecture was developed. This view shows an abstraction of the designed package composition for the system Level 3 components.

- **Infrastructure Folder** – This package is the outermost layer of the architecture. It includes the routes and persistence packages.
- **Interface Adapters Folder**– Contains sub-folders with the Adapters and Repositories interface implementations. Furthermore, controller implementations are part of this package, and they depend on the services' interfaces defined by the inner layer.
- **Application Services Folder** – This package specifies interfaces that the services, repositories, and adapters must implement. In addition, it includes a sub-folder with the implementation of application services interfaces. These services depend on the core Domain layer.
- **Domain Package** - Includes sub-folders with the system's aggregates, values, objects, and domain services. The package does not have any dependencies on other layers.

Figure 40 - Level 3 Implementation View

The Implementation design follows the structure previously mentioned in the Logical View design, and consequently, the Onion Architecture. Figure 41 depicts the mapping between the Level 3 Implementation and Logical Views.

Figure 41 - Level 3 Logical View vs Implementation View

4.2.3.3 Process View

The Level 3 Process View uses the UML sequence diagram notation to illustrate the design of the system use cases while also detailing the most interesting and complex features further.

4.2.3.3.1 UC1 - Register User

Regarding the creation of a user in the platform, the unregistered user needs to introduce all the required information through the Flexigy API. When the DTO reaches the service method responsible for creating users, it is first used to verify if a duplicate user is being entered (step 1.1.1.1 in figure 42 sequence diagram). Then, the mapper pattern is used to create the user domain objects directly from DTO objects (step 1.1.1.2), keeping the two layers independent from one another. Lastly, the information is saved in the database, and the user is informed.

Figure 42 - Sequence Diagram UC1: Register User

4.2.3.3.2 UC2 - Create Device

The creation of a device in the Flexigy system follows the same process and design characteristics as the previously presented use case. The respective system sequence diagram can be found in Appendix B for a matter of simplicity and ease of reading.

4.2.3.3.3 UC3 - Get Device Measurements

Concerning the feature that allows the system to fetch device measurements, the platform user can utilize the Flexigy API to request a specific device's historical data. After receiving the necessary input data, the *DeviceService* verifies the existence of the device. Then, it uses the *MeasurementsAdapter* (step 1.1.1.2 in the sequence diagram in figure 43) to communicate with an implementation of the *DevicesAPI* previously mentioned in the Level 1 Logical View of the system design (section 4.2.1.1). Ultimately, the fetched information is returned to the user using the mapper and DTO patterns.

Figure 43- Sequence Diagram UC3: Get Device Measurements

4.2.3.3.4 UC4 - Manually Create Flex Offers

The manual creation of a Flex Offer involves the input of a device energy profile. Figure 44 illustrates the process through a UML sequence diagram.

First, the user introduces a JSON containing all the needed information to create a Flex Offer successfully. Then, the system fetches the database for the corresponding device, and depending on its type, a different Flex Offer is created. Finally, the Flex Offer is saved in the system, and the user is informed of such.

Figure 44 - Sequence Diagram UC4: Manually Create Flex Offers

4.2.3.3.5 UC5 - Automatically Create Flex Offers

The automatic creation of Flex Offers is similar to its manual creation designed in the previous section. However, in this case, the user does not input the device's energy profile, being the system responsible for forecasting it efficiently.

As shown in figure 45, the design of this feature begins with the user utilizing the Flexigy API route to introduce the needed JSON information to the creation of a Flex Offer. After going through the controller, the request is handled by a specific service method in which the respective device is retrieved from the database (step 1.1.1.1 in figure 45 sequence diagram).

Next, the device energy profile is forecasted (step 1.1.1.2), and depending on the device type, the corresponding Flex Offer is created using the mapper pattern. In the end, the created Flex Offer is saved in the system database, and a response is sent back to the user.

Figure 45 - Sequence Diagram UC5: Automatically Create Flex Offers

4.2.3.3.6 UC5a - Forecast Device Energy Profile

For the automatic creation of a Flex Offer, the system itself predicts the device's energy profile. To do so, specific algorithms were used to implement a way to identify energy patterns. However, the algorithm for identifying an energy pattern depends on what kind of device it is. Figure 46 shows the three different device types addressed during the internship.

Figure 46 - Sequence Diagram UC5a: Forecast Device Energy Profile

If the device is a solar panel, the system recurs to an external API service to forecast its energy profile. Otherwise, if the device type is a wet device or refrigerator, algorithms from the paper “Generation and Evaluation of Flex Offer from Flexible Electrical Devices” [102] previously studied by Rafael Rocha in [103] were used as a way to predict the device's energy patterns.

4.2.3.3.7 UC6 - Schedule Day-Ahead Flex Offers

Given the project functional requirements and constraints, it was decided to split the day-ahead Flex Offer scheduling algorithm into three different levels:

- **Level 1** - This level aims to maximize the user's energy self-consumption, hence answering FR7. a.
- **Level 2** - Level 2 optimizes community energy consumptions based on users' profiles, thus responding to the FR7.
- **Level 3** - Level 3 aggregates community Flex Offers and sells the energy flexibility directly on the market.

Since level 1 is independently executed for each system user, it could be performed at the prosumer side in the future, thus distributing the algorithm's computational needs and consequently reducing the load on the community platform. Although the implementation of a distributed algorithm was not part of this internship's scope, the two-level separation enables one to plan future system expansions (NFR 5) and meet Flexigy's performance and scalability requirements (NFR1 and 3). This implementation also improves user's data privacy as each prosumer's data would be processed at the user side. Note that a real-world deployment of the platform would have to implement more concerns about RGPD [104] compliance.

Figure 47 illustrates how the optimization algorithm can be distributed among system players.

Figure 47 – Scheduling algorithm layers distributed among system players

In the following sections, we will go into more detail about the design of scheduling features addressed during the internship.

Since this is a day-ahead optimization algorithm, a system feature was designed to trigger the Community Energy Optimization Job each day at 10:30 PM (figure 48).

Figure 48 – Sequence Diagram UC6: Timer task job scheduling

Once the Community Energy Optimization Job is triggered, the scheduler service scheduleDayAheadFlexOffers() method is used to schedule day ahead Flex Offers. This method starts by forecasting the user’s day-ahead production and, later, executing the Level 1 and Level 2 optimization algorithms.

Figure 49 - Sequence Diagram UC6: Schedule Day Ahead Flex Offers

4.2.3.3.7.1 Level 1

Level 1 is executed for all the Flex Offers of non-Go-Ahead prosumers and aims to maximize their energy self-consumption while minimizing the total scheduling cost. By indication of the consortium, self-consumption energy was considered free.

Figure 50 shows the partial sequence diagram for this level. Firstly, the algorithm fetches community and grid prices for the day ahead. Secondly, for each user with a supplier profile other than Go-Ahead, the system tries to generate a self-production energy profile. If the user has self-production forecasted, the fixed, shiftable, and elastic Flex Offers are scheduled. Finally, a forecast of the buildings' unpredictable consumptions is generated (section 4.2.3.3.8), and the production profile is updated accordingly.

Figure 50 - Sequence Diagram UC6: Schedule Day Ahead Flex Offers Level 1

Algorithm 3 describes the solution designed to schedule fixed Flex Offers (step 1.5.1 in figure 50 sequence diagram).

Algorithm 3: `scheduleSelfConsumptionFixedFO`**Input:****fo** - Consumption Fixed Flex Offer**production** - Multidimensional array containing: (i) user production, (ii) energy prices for each time slice**user** - User**Output:****production** - The updated user production profile

```

1:  Function scheduleSelfConsumptionFixedFO (fo, production,
    user)
2:    auxTime <- fo.start
3:    energyProfile <- fo.getEnergyProfileToSchedule()
4:    schedule <- new Schedule(auxTime)
5:    For each energySlice in energyProfile Do
6:      energy2Schedule <- getMaxEnergyConsumption(production,
        auxTime, energySlice)
7:      If energy2Schedule > 0 Then
8:        schedule.AddSlice(auxTime, energy2Schedule)
9:      End if
10:     auxTime = auxTime + Program.TimeSliceSize
11:    End for
12:    production <- scheduleFlexOffer (schedule, production, fo)
13:    Return production
14:  End

```

Algorithm 3 - Level 1 Fixed Flex Offers scheduling algorithm

Given that a Fixed Flex Offer has no energy flexibility, its start date is considered the scheduling date (line 1). Next, for each energy slice of the Flex Offer energy profile, the algorithm verifies how much energy consumption can be scheduled using self-production (line 6). If some or all the energy can be scheduled using the self-production, a slice is added to the schedule.

Finally, at the *scheduleFlexOffer* method, both the Flex Offer and the production energy profile are updated, discounting the energy scheduled, and the Flex Offer schedule is saved in the database.

For further clarification of the fixed Flex Offer scheduling algorithm, a set of figures will be used to display the designed process in a visual manner. Figure 51 depicts a fixed Flex Offer profile (orange) and an energy production profile (blue) over the course of a day.

Figure 51 – Production profile and Fixed Flex Offer profile

Figure 52 shows both the Flex Offer (orange) and production (grey) energy profiles after the algorithm has iterated over all the time slices.

Figure 52 – Updated Production profile and Fixed Flex Offer profile

Finally, figure 53 helps to compare the initial production profile (blue) and the production profile that will be returned by the method (grey) after scheduling the Flex Offer.

Figure 53 – Comparison between the original and updated production profile

Algorithm 4 describes the algorithm designed to schedule shiftable Flex Offers (step 1.5.2 in figure 50 sequence diagram).

Algorithm 4: scheduleSelfConsumptionShiftableFO

Input:

fo - Consumption Shiftable Flex Offer

production - Multidimensional array containing: (i) user production, (ii) energy prices for each time slice

user - User

Output:

production - The updated user production profile

```

1:  Function scheduleSelfConsumptionShiftableFO (fo, production,
    user)
2:      consumptionPrice <- MAXVALUE
3:      energyProfile <- fo.getEnergyProfileToSchedule ()
4:      schedule <- new Schedule(auxTime)
5:      For i = fo.start; i < fo.end; i = i + Program.TimeSliceSize
    Do
6:          auxTime = i
7:          auxSchedule <- new Schedule(i)
8:          Sum <- 0
9:          energyProfile <- fo.getEnergyProfileToSchedule()
10:         For each energySlice In energyProfile Do
11:             energy2Schedule <- getMaxEnergyConsumption(production,
                auxTime, energySlice)
12:             consumptionSurplus = energySlice.energy-energy2Schedule
13:             sum = sum + checkprice(consumptionSurplus, auxTime, es)
14:             auxSchedule.AddSlice(auxTime, energy2Schedule)
15:             auxTime = auxTime + Program.TimeSliceSize
16:         End for
17:         If sum < consumptionPrice then
18:             schedule <- auxSchedule
19:             consumptionPrice <- sum
20:         End If
21:     End for
22:     production <- scheduleFlexOffer(schedule, production, fo)
23:     Return production
24: End

```

Algorithm 4 - Level 1 Shiftable Flex Offers scheduling algorithm

Algorithm: elasticHeuristicScheduling

Input:

deviceLiters - Liters of the thermoaccumulator
devicePower - Device power in kW
timeSliceTime - Time slice time in minutes
tMax - Maximum temperature within confort zone
tMin - Minimum temperature within confort zone
tStart - Inicial temperature
start - Start date time
end - End date time

Output:

consumptionProfile - Device consumption profile
deviceSchedule - Scheduled device actuations

```

1:  Function scheduleHeuristicElastic
2:    prices <- getEletricityPrices()
3:    waterDrawTimes <- forecastWaterDrawTimes()
4:    auxTime = start
5:    temperatureHelper = tStart
6:    totalCost <- 0
7:    While(auxtime < end) Do
8:      nextCoolDownTime = getNextCoolDownTime(tMin,
        temperatureHelper, auxtime, timeSliceTime)
9:      If isLowestPriceUntilNextCooldown(nextCoolDownTime,
        prices)Then
10:         newTemp <- calculateNewTemp()
11:         If newTemp < tMax Then
12:           temperatureHelper <- heatUp ()
            totalCost = totalCost + heatUpCost(prices,
            deviceLiters, devicePower)
13:         Else
14:           temperatureHelper <- coolDown()
15:         End
16:         End
17:         temperatureHelper <- coolDown()
18:       End While
19:       fitness = fitness -
        temperaturePenalizations(temperatureHelper, tMax, tMin) -
        totalCost
20:       Auxtime <- auxtime.AddMinutes(timeSliceTime);
21:     End

```

Algorithm: elasticGeneticScheduling

Input:

deviceLiters - Liters of the thermoaccumulator
devicePower - Device power in kW
timeSliceTime - Time slice time in minutes
tMax - Maximum temperature within confort zone
tMin - Minimum temperature within confort zone
tStart - Inicial temperature
start - Start date time
end - End date time

Output:

consumptionProfile - Device consumption profile
deviceSchedule - Scheduled device actuations

```
1: Function scheduleGeneticElastic
2:   chromosome <- new BinaryChromosome(24 *(60 / timeSliceTime))
3:   population <- new Population(POPULATION_NUMBER, chromosome)
4:   fitness <- new FuncFitness()
5:   selection <- new EliteSelectionMinimization()
6:   crossover <- new UniformCrossover(CROSS_OVER_RATE)
7:   mutation <- new FlipBitMutation()
8:   termination <- new fitnessStagnation(STAGNATION_NUMBER)
9:   genetic <- new Genetic(population, fitness, selection,
10:    crossover, mutation, termination)
11: End
```

Initially, a set of auxiliary variables is created. Then a cycle (lines 2 to 4) is executed to check in which of the time slices comprised between the flexibility start and end date it is more monetarily advantageous to start the execution of the Flex Offer consumption (lines 5 to 21).

Finally, the *scheduleFlexOffer* method saves the best schedule in the database and updates the Flex Offer and the self-production energy profile accordingly.

Again, for further clarification of the shiftable Flex Offer scheduling algorithm, a set of figures will be used to display the designed process in a visual manner. Figure 54 depicts a shiftable Flex Offer profile (blue) and an energy production profile (grey) over the course of a day. The red line marks the flexibility start and end hours. After receiving this data, the algorithm will test all the Flex Offer starting hour possibilities and pick the one with the lower estimated overall cost, considering auto consumption free and the forecasted energy prices.

Figure 54 - Production profile and Shiftable Flex Offer profile

Figure 5 shows the Flex Offer profile at the time that is more monetarily advantageous to start the execution of the Flex Offer consumption.

Figure 55 - Production profile and the best Shiftable Flex Offer profile

Figure 56 shows the Flex Offer energy profile before (light blue) and after (dark blue) the algorithm has been executed. This energy profile will be updated, the type change to fixed and saved accordingly in order to be scheduled in Level 2.

Figure 56 - Flex Offer energy profile before and after the algorithm has executed

Finally, figure 57 helps to compare the initial production profile (grey) and the production profile that will be returned by the method (green) after the Flex Offer schedule has been executed.

Figure 57 - Comparison between the original and updated production profile

4.2.3.3.7.2 Level 2

Level 2 starts by getting all unscheduled Flex Offers for a given date. Then, it collects the users' production surplus to generate a community energy production profile. Finally, the Flex Offer pending from the previous level are scheduled according to the user buyer profile and to the Flex Offer type (steps 2, 3, and 4 in the sequence diagram in figure 58).

Figure 58 - Sequence Diagram UC6: Schedule Day Ahead Flex Offers Level 2

Algorithm 5 describes the pseudocode designed to schedule the Level 2 Fixed Flex Offers (step 2 in the sequence diagram in figure 58).

Algorithm 5: scheduleFixedFO**Input:**

fo - Consumption Fixed Flex Offer

production - Multidimensional array containing: (i) community production, (ii) energy prices for each time slice

Output:

production - Updated production profile

```

1: Function scheduleFixedFO (fo, production)
2:   auxTime <- fo.start
3:   schedule <- new Schedule(auxTime)
4:   energyProfile <- fo.getEnergyProfileToSchedule()
5:   buyerProfile <- getFlexOfferUserProfile(fo)
6:   For each energySlice in energyProfile Do
7:     energy <- energySlice.energy
8:     If energy > 0 Then
9:       Schedule = scheduleSlice(auxTime, energy2Schedule, user
           production, schedule)
10:    End if
11:    auxTime = auxTime + Program.TimeSliceSize
12:  End for
13:  production <- scheduleFlexOffer(schedule, production, fo)
14:  Return production
15: End

```

Algorithm 5 - Level 2 Fixed Flex Offers scheduling algorithm

Once again, since a Fixed Flex Offer has no energy flexibility, its start date is considered the scheduling date (line 1). Then, the algorithm initializes a variable with the Flex Offer energy profile and another with the user buyer profile.

Next, the algorithm schedules each energy slice of the Flex Offer energy profile using the *scheduleSlice* method. This method, analyzed further ahead in algorithm 7, guarantees an adequate energy schedule according to the user profile.

Finally, at the *scheduleFlexOffer* method, both the Flex Offer and the production energy profile are updated, discounting the energy scheduled, and the Flex Offer schedule is saved in the database.

Algorithm 6 describes the pseudocode designed to schedule the Level 2 Shiftable Flex Offers (step 3 in the sequence diagram in figure 58).

Algorithm 6: scheduleShiftableFO**Input:**

fo - Consumption Shiftable Flex Offer

production - Multidimensional array containing: (i) community production, (ii) energy prices for each time slice

Output:

production - Updated production profile

```

1: Function scheduleSelfConsumptionShiftableFO (fo, production,
  user)
2:   consumptionPrice <- MAXVALUE
3:   energyProfile <- fo.getEnergyProfileToSchedule ()
4:   schedule <- new Schedule(auxTime)
5:   buyerProfile <- getFlexOfferUserBuyerProfile(fo)
6:   For i = fo.start; i < fo.end; i = i + Program.TimeSliceSize
   Do
7:     auxTime = i
8:     auxSchedule <- new Schedule(i)
9:     sum <- 0
10:    energyProfile <- fo.getEnergyProfileToSchedule()
11:    For each energySlice in energyProfile Do
12:      energy <- energySlice.energy
13:      If energy > 0 Then
14:        auxSchedule = scheduleSlice(auxTime, energy2Schedule,
          buyerProfile, production, auxSchedule)
15:        sum = sum + auxSchedule.getPrice(auxTime);
16:      End If
17:      auxTime = auxTime + Program.TimeSliceSize
18:    End for
19:    If sum < consumptionPrice Then
20:      schedule <- auxSchedule
21:      consumptionPrice <- sum
22:    End If
23:  End for
24:  production <- scheduleFlexOffer(schedule, production, fo)
25:  Return production
26: End

```

Algorithm 6 - Level 2 Shiftable Flex Offers scheduling algorithm

Initially, a set of auxiliary variables is created. Then a cycle (lines 6 to 23) is executed to check in which of the time slices comprised between the flexibility start and end date it is more monetarily advantageous to start the execution of the Flex Offer consumption (lines 19 to 22).

Finally, the *scheduleFlexOffer* method saves the best schedule in the database and updates the Flex Offer and the production energy profile accordingly

Algorithm 7 describes the *scheduleSlice* method used in the previous algorithms in pseudocode.

Algorithm 7: scheduleSlice**Input:**

auxTime - Time to schedule the energy

energy2Schedule - Energy amount to schedule

buyerProfile - User buyer profile

auxSchedule - Multidimensional array containing the schedule for each of the Flex Offer slices

production - Multidimensional array containing: (i) community production, (ii) energy prices for each time slice

Output:

schedule - Schedule updated with the new slice

```

1: Function scheduleSlice (auxTime, energy2Schedule, buyerProfile,
  production, auxSchedule)
2:   For each timeSlice in production do
3:     energySources <- timeSlice.energySources ()
4:     Case based on buyerProfile
5:       Case "Bold"
6:         auxSchedule <- scheduleSliceBoldProfile(auxSchedule,
  energySources, energy2Schedule, auxTime)
7:       Case "Cautious"
8:         auxSchedule <-
  scheduleSliceCautiousProfile(auxSchedule,
  energySources, energy2Schedule, auxTime)
9:       Case "Community"
10:        auxSchedule <-
  scheduleSliceCommunityProfile(auxSchedule,
  energySources, energy2Schedule, auxTime)
11:      End Case
12:    End For
13:    Return auxSchedule
14: End

```

Algorithm 7 - Level 2 scheduleSlice method

This method is used to schedule each energy slice accordingly to the user buyer profile:

- If the user's consumption profile is **Bold**, the *scheduleSliceBoldProfile* method will choose the lowest cost option among the renewable production sources (i.e., local community or grid identified as renewable).
- If the user's consumption profile is **Cautious**, the *scheduleSliceCautiousProfile* method will schedule the slice consumption as cheaply as possible, considering all available energy sources (i.e., renewable and non-renewable grid, community)
- If the user's consumption profile is **Community**, the *scheduleSliceCommunityProfile* method will try to maximize consumption at the community level.

4.2.3.3.8 UC6a - Forecast building unpredictable energy consumption

In order to maximize the users' self-consumption, the system needed a way to accurately forecast the unpredictable consumptions not stated in the Flex Offers (e.g., charging a computer, using the coffee machine, turning on the TV).

When called by the Level1 scheduler, the *getBuildingForecastedEnergyProfile* gets the user's building device and then fetches the device's historical consumption data. Finally, a forecasting algorithm is used to create and return an energy forecast;

Figure 59 – Sequence Diagram UC6a: Forecast building unpredictable energy consumption

One of the most important details to consider when forecasting buildings' energy consumption is their daily utilization pattern. For example, an office building is mainly used during workdays when people go to work and practically closed at weekends and holidays, which means the building has different consumption profiles accordingly to the type of day.

Because of it, the designed algorithm begins by weighting the building historical data differently if the day to be forecasted is: (i) a holiday, (ii) a weekend, or (iii) a workday. Next, a weighted arithmetic mean is conducted for all the daily time slices, and a forecasted energy profile is returned.

Algorithm 8 presents the design of the *forecastBuildingConsumption* method in pseudocode (step 1.3 in the sequence diagram of figure 59).

Algorithm 8: forecastBuildingConsumption

Input:

historicalMeasurements - Multidimensional array with the building historical consumptions

date - Date of the forecast

Output:

energyProfile - Multidimensional array with the forecasted energy consumption

```
1: Function forecastBuildingConsumption(historicalMeasurements, date)
2:   Case based on date
3:     Case date is Public Holiday
4:       weightedHistoricalData <-
         holidayWeightedHistoricalData(measurements, date)
5:     Case date is Weekend
6:       weightedHistoricalData <-
         weekendWeightedHistoricalData(measurements, date)
7:     Case date is Workday
8:       weightedHistoricalData <-
         workdayWeightedHistoricalData(measurements, date)
9:   End Case
10:  energyProfile <-
        weightedMeanEnergySlices(weightedHistoricalData)
11:  Return energyProfile
12: End
```

Algorithm 8 – Forecast Building consumption method

Algorithm 9 describes the designed approach to weight historical data for predicting a holiday energy profile. The methods for forecasting weekends or workdays are similar to this method, adjusting only how the weight is distributed. Their implementation can be found in Appendices C, D, and E.

Algorithm 9: holidayWeightedHistoricalData**Input:** historicalMeasurements**historicalMeasurements** - Multidimensional array with the building historical consumptions**Output:** energyProfile**energyProfile** - Multidimensional array with a collection of each daily time slice energy value and their corresponding weight.

```

1: Function holidayWeightedHistoricalData (historicalMeasurements,
date)
2:   sortMeasurementsFromNewestToOldest(historicalMeasurements)
3:   auxTime <- 00H
4:   Dictionary <- new
5:   While auxTime<24H Do
6:     holidayWeight <- HOLIDAY_HOLIDAY_WEIGHT;
7:     weekendWeight <- WEEKEND_HOLIDAY_WEIGHT;
8:     Dictionary.Add(auxTime, 0)
9:     For each measurement in Measurements Do
10:      If measurement.Time = auxTime Then
11:        If measurement.Date is PublicHoliday Then
12:          Dictionary[auxtime].Add(energy, holidayWeight)
13:          If holidayWeight > HOLIDAY_HOLIDAY_WEIGHT/2 Then
14:            holidayWeight <- holidayWeight - DECREASE_WEIGHT;
15:          End If
16:        Else If measurement.Date is Weekend Then
17:          Dictionary[auxtime].Add(energy, weekendWeight)
18:          If weekendWeight > WEEKEND_HOLIDAY_WEIGHT/2 Then
19:            weekendWeight <- weekendWeight - DECREASE_WEIGHT;
20:          End If
21:        End If
22:      End If
23:    End For
24:    auxTime <- auxTime + Program.TimeSliceSize
25:  End While
26:  Return energyProfile
27: End

```

Algorithm 9 – holidayWeightedHistoricalData method pseudocode

In this case, the algorithm starts by sorting the measurements from the newest to the oldest ones (line 2). This step is done because we decided to give more weight to historically closer values, as they can represent the building consumption reality better than older ones.

Then, for each daily time slice (line 5), two auxiliary variables holding the initial weights to attribute to measurements are created. Note that these are system variables to allow easy changeability. For example, when forecasting a holiday energy profile, we have decided to

give the majority of the weight to other holidays in the historical data and a lower weight to weekends.

Next, for each of the measurements, if the measurement time corresponds to the daily time slice time, the algorithm checks the measurement day type. For example, if the measurement is from a holiday, a dictionary entry is added and the weight reduced for the next iterations, attributing less weight to historically older measurements.

Then, the result comes in the form of an energy profile that represents for each daily time slice a collection of weighted energy values and their corresponding weight. In the end, for each of the daily time slices of the weighted data, the weighted mean equation (Equation 1) is applied to the collection of weighted values, predicting an energy consumption.

Equation 1 - Weighted Mean

$$W = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i X_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i}$$

, where W is the resulting weighted average (in this case the predicted slice consumption); n is the number of terms to be averaged; W_i is the weight value (weights attributed during the previous phase) applied to x ; X_i is the data values to be averaged (past energy consumption values).

Table 16 shows an example of the weighted mean applied for some example energy slices in order to further clarify the designed method to forecast the energy consumption of a building.

Table 16 – Weighted Mean calculation example

Time Slice Hour	Weighted Values (value x weight)	Slice Weighted Mean
03:45 AM	3x1; 4x0.7; 2x0.5; 1x0.1; 5x0.05	3.04255319
04:00 AM	5x1; 6x0.7; 3x0.5; 5x0.1; 2x0.05	4.80851064
04:15 AM	2x1; 4.6x0.7; 4x0.5; 1x0.1; 2x0.05	3.15744681
04:30 AM	7x1; 9x0.9; 5x0.7; 8x0.5; 9x0.1; 8x0.05	7.24615385
04:45 AM	5x1; 5x0.7; 7x0.5; 1.5x0.1; 2x0.05	5.21276596

4.2.3.3.9 UC7 – Make EDM requests

After reviewing the EDM state of the art (section 2.2.2), and given the experimental nature of this use case, one decided to design it the most generically way possible, handling requests to either increase or decrease energy consumption.

Figure 60 shows the designed sequence diagram for this feature.

Figure 60 - Sequence Diagram UC7: Make EDM Request

Given the FR8.a. where the consortium states that the platform must prioritize EDM services, one decided that when the TSO requests an EDM service to reduce energy consumption for a given amount of time, the system should try to fulfill it by:

- Postpone the Flex Offers scheduled to start during the EDM request time.
- Turn off devices accordingly to their maximum turn-off minutes property.

In the case of an EDM request to increase energy consumption for a given amount of time, we have decided that the system should try to fulfill it by anticipating the Flex Offers.

In the design of this use case, we identified the need to use the Builder Pattern [105], as according to the domain rules, there is no use case to add actuations to an EDMRequest object, being the instance conceptually created instantly for a list of actuations.

The builder pattern allows the construction of an EDMRequest entity during the algorithm execution, facilitating the addition of actuations to it. At the end of the process, the builder returns the validated and domain rules compliant instance.

A more detailed sequence diagram design for both the reduction (step 1.1.1.1 in the sequence diagram of figure 60) and increase (step 1.1.1.2) of energy consumption can be found in Appendices F and G, respectively.

4.2.3.3.10 UC8 - Create Daily Actuation Schedule

This time-based feature is run once a day in order to create an actuation profile based on the Flex Offer scheduling. Figure 61 shows the design of a system feature to trigger the *DailyActuationSchedulingJob* each day at 11:30 PM.

Figure 61 - Sequence Diagram UC8: Timer task job scheduling

Figure 62 shows the process designed to create the actuation schedule. Once the *DailyActuationSchedulingJob* is triggered, a system service is used to fetch all the scheduled Flex Offers of a given date (step 1.2). Then for each of the scheduled Flex Offer time slices, the amount of energy scheduled is tested. If greater than 0, the system will create an actuation to turn the device on; otherwise, if the energy is 0, the actuation action is to turn the device OFF. In the end, all the created device actuations are used to instantiate a new *DailyDeviceActuation* object, and later all the information is saved in the database.

Figure 62 - Sequence Diagram UC9: Create Daily Actuation Schedule

4.2.3.3.11 UC9 – Perform Scheduled Device Actuations

This feature was designed to once every minute check and perform the needed device actuations. Figure 63 shows the process developed to trigger the *DeviceActuationJob* each minute.

Figure 63 - Sequence Diagram UC9: Timer task job scheduling

When the *DeviceActuationJob* is triggered, the system fetches the database for all the actuations scheduled for that given time (step 1.1 in the sequence diagram of figure 64). Then according to the actions specified, the system is designed to use the *DeviceAdapter* to send the turn On/Off command to the device via the *Devices API*.

Figure 64 - Sequence Diagram UC9: Perform Scheduled Device Actuations

4.2.3.3.12 UC10 - Show Flex Offer Energy Profile

This use case design allows the user to see the Flex Offer energy profile in the chosen visualization platform, Grafana. Firstly, the user uses the Flexigy API is to request this feature, sending all the necessary data. After the system has verified that the device exists (step 1.1.1.1 in the sequence diagram in figure 65), all of its Flex Offers falling under the specified search criteria are returned from the database (step 1.1.1.2). Then a *TimeSeriesResponseDTO* is created to send the data back to the visualization platform.

Figure 65 - Sequence Diagram UC10: Show Flex Offer Energy Profile

Given the similarity of the design of all the visualization use cases, and for the sake of simplicity and readability of the report, the sequence diagrams of UC11, UC12, and UC13 are on Appendices H, I, and J, respectively.

4.3 Chapter summary

This chapter documented the project architectural design while also presenting a new software data structure. The architectural design representation was done using a combination of the C4 model and the 4+1 model, which means different detail levels were used to describe the system. In Level 1, the system's bigger picture was provided, and the use cases were identified. In Level 2, the system containers were further described. In Level 3, the system was analyzed with finer detail, illustrating its implementation, its Onion-compliant architectural design, and its processes while also presenting the design of the most important system features and algorithms.

5 Implementation

This chapter begins by describing the choices made from a technology standpoint. Then, an overview of the system setup is presented. Finally, the implementation of the solutions is explained through a set of code snippets and screenshots, thus proving the effective implementation of the system design.

5.1 Technologies

After studying different technologic solutions to implement the Flexigy platform in the state-of-the-art (section 2.5), it was decided to adopt the .NET Core as the web API back-end technology because: (i) the consortium systems, where the platform aims to be integrated in the future, use .Net Core; (ii) there was previous knowledge related to its use, which allowed focusing on the development of a better solution and reducing the time to adapt to the platform.

For data persistence, a relational object mapper native in the .NET framework (Entity Framework) was used since it fully integrates with the .NET Core technology and reduces the object mapping time, thus leading one to implement a relational database solution, in this case, SQL Server.

Given the limited time to develop and implement the Flexigy platform during this internship, Grafana was the chosen visualization platform since it is an already built data visualization platform with easy integration capabilities and time-series focus.

Visual Studio Code was used as an integrated development environment since it allows implementing solutions in .NET Core, using the C# programming language.

5.2 Flexigy System Setup

Regarding the setup of the Flexigy system in a development environment, some specifics must be considered. Appendix K presents a setup guide that goes into detail about these aspects.

5.3 System Required API's

According to the Flexigy architecture, the system needs three APIs to function correctly: the Solar Forecast API, the Devices API, and the Price API.

In talks with the consortium, it was decided that they would make the devices and prices features available through two different endpoints present in one of their platforms, VPS's API.

5.3.1 VPS API Login

The first step needed to connect to the consortium API was to log in, obtaining a Token that would be needed for all future communications between the Flexigy platform and the Devices and Prices APIs. For this, a system adapter executed every time the application is started was implemented in the Interface Adapters Layer following the specified Interface defined in the Application Business Layer, thus complying with the designed Onion Architecture for the system. The specific Json and endpoints are omitted in the code snippet 1 for security purposes.

```
namespace Flexigy.Adapter.Adapters
{
    public class VpsLoginAdapter : IVpsLoginAdapter
    {
        private static readonly HttpClient client = new HttpClient();
        private readonly IHttpContextAccessor _httpContextAccessor;
        public VpsLoginAdapter(IHttpContextAccessor httpContextAccessor)
        {
            _httpContextAccessor = httpContextAccessor;
        }
        public VpsLoginAdapter()
        {
        }
        public async Task<string> login(string username, string password)
        {
            try
            {
                string myJson = << Omitted for security purposes>>;
                String url = new VPSAdapter().apiUrl;
                var response = await client.PostAsync(url, new StringContent(myJson, Encoding.UTF8, "application/json"));
                dynamic data = JObject.Parse(response.Content.ReadAsStringAsync().GetAwaiter().GetResult());
                return data.Token;
            }
        }
    }
}
```

Code Snippet 1 - VPS API Login

5.3.2 Devices API

The Devices API relies on the VPS IoT devices installed. In the Flexigy project, two different kinds of devices were used: a smart plug (left part of figure 66) and a transmitter (right part of figure 66). While the smart plug can read a device's consumed energy and turn On/Off the device's power, the transmitter can only read a device's energy consumptions.

Figure 66 – Left: VPS Smart Plug; Right: VPS Transmitter

These two devices send their aggregated data to a gateway named Cloogy (figure 67), which sends it to VPS servers, where the Flexigy platform will connect for the Devices API.

Figure 67 – VPS Cloogy gateway

In VPS's platform, each device is identified by a unique Tag, which means that Flexigy needs to specify the device's Tag to request any information from the API. Note that when designing the Flexigy data structure, it was decided that a Device registered in the platform should always be identified by a unique Tag corresponding to the VPS's device Tag.

Code snippet 2 shows the *IDeviceAdapter* Interface developed to establish the needed methods that all *DeviceAdapter* implementations should have.

```
namespace Flexigy.Application.IAdapters
{
    public interface IDeviceAdapter
    {
        List<Measurement> getTagMeasurements(Tag tag, DateTime from , DateTime
to);
        Task<bool> actuateOnDevice(Tag tag, bool action);
    }
}
```

Code Snippet 2 – Device Adapter Interface

The interface enables the following two system features:

- Turn On/Off the devices – This feature allows the Flexigy platform to control devices, for example, in use case 9, to perform scheduled use case actuations.
- Get the device's historical measurements – This feature is greatly needed by the system, as it is used in use cases such as forecasting buildings' unpredictable consumptions. Code snippet 3 presents the implemented *getTagMeasurements* method.

```

namespace Flexigy.Adapter.Adapters
{
    public class DeviceAdapter : IDeviceAdapter
    {
        private VPSAdapter mdr = new VPSAdapter();
        private static readonly HttpClient client = new HttpClient();
        private readonly IHttpContextAccessor _httpContextAccessor;
        public ConsumptionAdapter(IHttpContextAccessor httpContextAccessor)
        {
            _httpContextAccessor = httpContextAccessor;
        }

        public List<Measurement> getTagMeasurements(Tag tag, DateTime fromDate1, DateTime toDate2)
        {
            try
            {
                HttpResponseMessage response = (HttpResponseMessage)Request.CreateGetRequest("Endpoint omitted for security purposes"+ Program.SEARCH_GRANULARITY + "?to=" + DateTimeConverter.ConvertToUnixTimestamp(toDate2) + "&from=" + DateTimeConverter.ConvertToUnixTimestamp(fromDate1) + "&tags=[" + Int32.Parse(tag.Value) + "]", Program.API_TOKEN).GetResponse();

                string myResponse = "";
                using (System.IO.StreamReader sr = new System.IO.StreamReader(response.GetResponseStream()))
                {
                    myResponse = sr.ReadToEnd();
                    dynamic responseArray = JObject.Parse(myResponse);
                    List<Measurement> list = new List<Measurement>();
                    for (int i = 0; i < responseArray.Count; i++)
                    {
                        var item = (JObject)responseArray[i];
                        dynamic con = JObject.Parse(item.ToString());
                        var cons = new Measurement(new Energy((double)con.Read(), DateTimeConverter.ConvertFromUnixTimestamp((double)con.Date)));
                        list.Add(cons);
                    }
                    return list;
                }
            }
            catch (Exception e)
            {
                throw new System.ArgumentException("Error getting measurements" + e.Message);
            }
        }
    }
}

```

Code Snippet 3 – Device Adapter implementation

5.3.3 Price API

As stated earlier, electricity prices are also obtained from the VPS API. Code Snippet 4 shows the `getPrices` method of the Price Adapter implementation for the Flexigy platform. This method queries VPS API by using a special Tag given by the consortium and stored as a configurable constant in the platform.

```
public List<Tuple<DateTime, double>> getPrices(DateTime from , DateTime to)
{
    try
    {
        HttpResponseMessage response = (HttpResponse)Request.createGetRequest("Endpoint omitted for security purposes"
            + Program.SEARCH_GRANULARITY + "?to=" + DateTimeConverter.ConvertToUnixTimestamp(to)
            + "&from=" + DateTimeConverter.ConvertToUnixTimestamp(from)
            + "&tags=[" + Program.OMIE_TAG + "]", Program.API_TOKEN).GetResponse();

        string myResponse = "";
        List<Tuple<DateTime, double>> prices = new List<Tuple<DateTime, double>>();
        using (System.IO.StreamReader sr = new System.IO.StreamReader(response.GetResponseStream()))
        {
            myResponse = sr.ReadToEnd();
            dynamic responseArray = JObject.Parse(myResponse);
            for (int i = 0; i < responseArray.Count; i++)
            {
                var item = (JObject)responseArray[i];
                dynamic con = JObject.Parse(item.ToString());
                DateTime dt = DateTimeConverter.ConvertFromUnixTimestamp((double)con.Date);
                var price = new Tuple<DateTime, double>( new DateTime(from.Year, from.Month, from.Day, dt.Hour, dt.Minute, dt.Second),
                    (double)con.Read);
                prices.Add(price);
            }
            return prices;
        }
    }
    catch (Exception)
    {
        throw new System.ArgumentException("Error getting prices");
    }
}
```

Code Snippet 4 – Adapter implementation to get energy prices

Figure 68 shows the electricity prices for a given day in the Grafana data visualization platform created for the Flexigy project (Flexigy Use Case 13).

Figure 68 – Price profile of three different energy suppliers for a given day

Note that even though VPS API only returns a single price profile for a given day (Community Price Profile represented in green in figure 68), two other daily price profiles are simulated due to the needs of the UC6 scheduling algorithm. One represents the price for a renewable energies grid supplier (orange price profile in figure 68), and another the price profile to a more traditional grid supplier (blue price profile in figure 68).

5.3.4 Solar Forecast API

At an earlier project development stage, the Flexigy consortium stayed in charge of implementing a feature from their API side for the Flexigy platform to forecast the day-ahead solar production. Given that the feature was not made available until the time of writing, one decided that all the production profiles used to test other functionalities would be simulated.

Nonetheless, code snippet 5 displays the developed Interface to serve as a method contract for future implementations of an adapter for this feature. Note that this interface is stored in the Application Business Layer folder in order to follow the Onion Architectural pattern.

```
namespace Flexigy.Application.IAdapters
{
    public interface IProductionForecastAdapter
    {
        Task<List<EnergySlice>> getForecast(Tag tag, DateTime start, DateTime
end);
    }
}
```

Code Snippet 5 – Interface for production adapter

Figure 69 shows a user production profile for a given day in the Grafana data visualization platform, thus responding to Use Case 12.

Figure 69 – User production profile

5.4 Forecast Device Energy Profile

For the automatic creation of Flex Offers, the system itself generates the device’s energy consumption profile based on its historical consumption data. To do so, certain algorithms from the paper “Generation and Evaluation of Flex Offer from Flexible Electrical Devices” [102] previously studied by Rafael Rocha in [103] were used to implement a way to predict energy patterns depending on what kind of device it is.

As stated in the design section 4.2.3.3.6, the system implements features to predict the energy profile of three different device types. Code snippet 6 shows the implementation of one of the algorithms, the `forecastWetDeviceEnergyProfile` method.

```
private async Task<List<Measurement>> forecastWetDeviceConsumptions(Tag tag)
{
    List<Measurement> measurements = _measurementAdapter.getTagMeasurements(tag,
    DateTime.Today.AddDays(-Program.HISTORICAL), DateTime.Today.AddDays(-1));

    //Pattern Sequence Matcher to the wet-device
    var patterns = PSMWetDevices(measurements);
    //Energy profile method based on inserted patterns
    List<Measurement> es = energyProfileWetDevice(patterns);
    return es;
}
```

Code Snippet 6 – `forecastWetDeviceConsumptions` method

5.5 Forecast Building Unpredictable Energy Consumption

The forecast of the buildings' unpredictable energy consumption feature was implemented following the design decisions and guidelines discussed in section 4.2.3.3.8. Code snippet 7 demonstrates part of the implementation of this feature in the Flexigy platform.

```
private async Task<List<Measurement>> forecastBuildingConsumptions(Tag tag, DateTime date)
{
    //Get Past measurements
    List<Measurement> measurements = _measurementAdapter.getTagMeasurements(tag, DateTime.Today.AddDays(-Program.HISTORICAL_DAYS), DateTime.Today.AddDays(-1));
    //Daily TimeSlices
    List<DateTime> ts = getDayTimeSlices(date);
    //Create dictionary
    Dictionary<DateTime, List<Tuple<double, double>>> dict = new Dictionary<DateTime, List<Tuple<double, double>>>();
    foreach (DateTime dt in ts)
    {
        dict.Add(dt, new List<Tuple<double, double>>());
    }

    //sort measurements from newest to oldest
    measurements.Sort(delegate (Measurement x, Measurement y)
    {
        return x.measurementTime.CompareTo(y.measurementTime);
    });
    var tomorrow = date;
    if (DateSystem.IsPublicHoliday(tomorrow, CountryCode.PT))
    {
        dict = holidayWeightedHistoryData(measurements, dict, tomorrow);
    }
    else if (DateSystem.IsWeekend(tomorrow, CountryCode.PT))
    {
        dict = weekendWeightedHistoryData(measurements, dict, tomorrow);
    }
    else
    { //WorkDay
        dict = workdayWeightedHistoryData(measurements, dict, tomorrow);
    }
    List<Measurement> es = weightedMeanEnergySlices(dict);
    return es;
}
```

Code Snippet 7 – forecastBuildingUnpredictableConsumption method

5.6 Schedule Day-Ahead Flex Offers

Regarding the UC6 schedule of day-ahead Flex offers, its implementation followed the designed multi-level structure. Code snippets 8 and 9 show part of the implementation of the Level 1 and Level 2 Flex Offer scheduling, respectively. Appendices L to P displays more of this feature implementation according to the design in section 4.2.3.3.7.

```
private async Task<bool> scheduleSelfConsumption(List<ConsumptionFlexOffer> flexOffers, ProductionProfile production, User user, DateTime start, DateTime end)
{
    List<ConsumptionFlexOffer> fixedFlexOffers = new List<ConsumptionFlexOffer>();
    List<ConsumptionFlexOffer> shiftableFlexOffers = new List<ConsumptionFlexOffer>();
    List<ConsumptionFlexOffer> elasticFlexOffers = new List<ConsumptionFlexOffer>();

    foreach (ConsumptionFlexOffer fo in flexOffers)
    {
        switch (fo.toScheduleProfile.type.type)
        {
            case "Fixed":
                fixedFlexOffers.Add(fo);
                break;
            case "Shiftable":
                shiftableFlexOffers.Add(fo);
                break;
            case "Elastic":
                elasticFlexOffers.Add(fo);
                break;
        }
    }

    foreach (ConsumptionFlexOffer fo in fixedFlexOffers)
    {
        _logger.LogInformation("SL1: Scheduling Fixed FO " + fo.name.name + " ID: " + fo.Id.Value + " Device: " + fo.deviceId);
        try
        {
            production = await scheduleSelfConsumptionFixedFO(fo, production, user);
        }
        catch (Exception e)
        {
            _logger.LogInformation("SL1: It was not possible to schedule Fixed FO " + fo.name.name + " ID: " + fo.Id.Value + " Device: " + fo.deviceId + e.Message);
        }
    }
}
```

```
        foreach (ConsumptionFlexOffer fo in shiftableFlexOffers)
        {
            _logger.LogInformation("SL1: Scheduling Shiftable FO " + fo.name.name + " ID: " + fo.Id.Value + " Device: " + fo.deviceId);
            try
            {
                production = await scheduleSelfConsumptionShiftableFO(fo, production, user);
            }
            catch (Exception e)
            {
                _logger.LogInformation("SL1: It was not possible to schedule Shiftable FO " + fo.name.name + " ID: " + fo.Id.Value + " Device: " + fo.deviceId + e.Message);
            }
            _logger.LogInformation("SL1: Reserving Unpredictable Consumption Margin");
            try
            {
                production = await reserveUnpredictableConsumptionMargin(production, user, start);
            }
            catch (Exception e)
            {
                _logger.LogInformation("SL1: It was not possible to reserve an unpredictable consumption margin" + e.Message);
            }

            try
            {
                await _productionService.updateUserProduction(production, user, start, end);
            }
            catch (Exception e)
            {
                _logger.LogInformation("SL1: It was not possible to update user production. All scheduled FO will be removed" + e.Message);
            }
            return true;
        }
    }
```

Code Snippet 8 – Level 1 scheduleSelfConsumption method

```

public async Task<bool> scheduleLevel2(DateTime start, DateTime end)
{
    _logger.LogInformation("SCHEDULING LEVEL 2 (SL2) from " + start.ToString() + " to " + end.ToString());
    List<ConsumptionFlexOffer> flexOffers = await _flexOfferService.getUnscheduledConsumptionFlexOffers(start, end);
    ProductionProfile production = await _productionService.getLevel2ProductionProfile(start, end);
    List<ConsumptionFlexOffer> fixedFlexOffers = new List<ConsumptionFlexOffer>();
    List<ConsumptionFlexOffer> shiftableFlexOffers = new List<ConsumptionFlexOffer>();
    List<ConsumptionFlexOffer> elasticFlexOffers = new List<ConsumptionFlexOffer>();

    foreach (ConsumptionFlexOffer fo in flexOffers)
    {
        switch (fo.toScheduleProfile.type.type)
        {
            case "Fixed":
                fixedFlexOffers.Add(fo);
                break;
            case "Shiftable":
                shiftableFlexOffers.Add(fo);
                break;
            case "Elastic":
                elasticFlexOffers.Add(fo);
                break;
        }
    }
    foreach (ConsumptionFlexOffer fo in fixedFlexOffers)
    {
        logger.LogInformation("SL2: Scheduling Fixed FO " + fo.name.name + " ID: " + fo.Id.Value + " Device: " + fo.deviceId);
        try
        {
            production = await scheduleFixedFO(fo, production);
        }
        catch (Exception e)
        {
            _logger.LogInformation("SL2: It was not possible to schedule Fixed FO " + fo.name.name + " ID: " + fo.Id.Value + " Device: " + fo.deviceId + e.Message);
        }
    }
}

```

Code Snippet 9 – Level 2 scheduleLevel2 method

Also, regarding the schedule of Flex Offers, Figure 70 shows the implemented Grafana user interface to visualize the algorithms results (Flexigy Use Case 11). It is possible to see that, for example, the Fixed Flex Offer presented, whose energy profile is illustrated in green, has been partially scheduled with the user's self-production in Level 1, depicted by the yellow stripes in the figure. A more thorough analysis and a test scenario will be conducted for this system feature in chapter 6.

Figure 70 – Fixed Flex Offer scheduling

5.7 Handle EDM Requests

For the implementation of the EDM requests service, we followed the designed concepts in section 4.2.3.3.9. Code snippet 10 shows an implementation of the EDMRequest method, where a case based on the request action is made.

```
public async Task<EDMResponseDto> EDMRequest(EDMdto dto)
{
    switch (dto.action)
    {
        case "Decrease":
            return await this.reduceConsumption(dto.energy, dto.minutes);
        case "Increase":
            return await this.increaseConsumption(dto.energy, dto.minutes);
        default:
            _logger.LogInformation("EDM action is not recognized");
            throw new System.Exception("EDM action is not recognized ");
    }
}
```

Code Snippet 10 – EDMRequest method

Figure 71 shows an example of the system logging messages during the event of a decrease consumption EDM request. In this case, the system cannot fulfill the request since there is no Flex Offer available to postpone during the request time. In addition, the devices connected to the platform are not consuming enough energy to satisfy the needs of the TSO.

```

2021-06-22 00:11:30.4359 |INFO|----- REGULATING RESERVE REQUEST RECEIVED -> Type Decrease, 0,11 Kwh in 15 minutes
2021-06-22 00:11:40.5398 |INFO|There are no scheduled flex offers starting in the next 15 minutes
2021-06-22 00:11:46.9660 |INFO|Device 3927 Consumption: 0,006 kwh
2021-06-22 00:11:47.3411 |INFO|Device 4768 Consumption: 0,015 kwh
2021-06-22 00:11:47.9644 |INFO|Device 4961 Consumption: 0,003 kwh
2021-06-22 00:11:48.7329 |INFO|Device 4970 Consumption: 0,006 kwh
2021-06-22 00:11:53.0904 |INFO|Impossible to fullfill the request

```

Figure 71 – System logs for an EDM consumption decrease request

On the other hand, figure 72 demonstrates an EDM request successfully fulfilled and the corresponding devices' actuations.

```

2021-06-22 00:23:02.9264 |INFO|----- REGULATING RESERVE REQUEST RECEIVED -> Type Decrease, 0,015 Kwh in 15 minutes
2021-06-22 00:23:03.2659 |INFO|There are no scheduled flex offers starting in the next 15 minutes |
2021-06-22 00:23:03.6008 |INFO|Device 103 Consumption: 0,001 kwh |
2021-06-22 00:23:06.7313 |INFO|Device 3927 Consumption: 0,007 kwh |
2021-06-22 00:23:07.3138 |INFO|Device 4768 Consumption: 0,014 kwh |
2021-06-22 00:23:07.3828 |INFO|Request fulfilled and actuations updated |
2021-06-22 00:24:00.0152 |INFO|----- Starting Actuations - 0:24h ----- |
2021-06-22 00:24:00.0919 |INFO| Device OFF 103 |
2021-06-22 00:24:00.0919 |INFO| Device OFF 4768 |
2021-06-22 00:24:00.0919 |INFO| Device OFF 3927 |
2021-06-22 00:25:00.0074 |INFO|----- Starting Actuations - 0:25h ----- |
2021-06-22 00:26:00.0141 |INFO|----- Starting Actuations - 0:26h ----- |
2021-06-22 00:26:00.0806 |INFO| Device ON 103 |
2021-06-22 00:26:00.0806 |INFO| Device ON 4768 |
2021-06-22 00:26:00.0858 |INFO| Device ON 3927 |

```

Figure 72 - System logs for a successful EDM request

5.8 Visualization Use Cases

Since it was decided to work with the Grafana visualization tool, it was necessary to implement a solution to connect it to the Flexigy back-end. To do so, we installed a new Grafana data source plugin that enables the platform to fetch the Flexigy data through a RESTful API [106].

Figure 73 shows the configuration of this plugin with the Flexigy URL.

The screenshot displays the Grafana configuration page for a data source named 'Flexigy'. The page is titled 'Data Sources / Flexigy' and indicates the source type is 'JSON'. A 'Settings' dropdown menu is visible. The configuration is organized into sections: 'Name' (Flexigy, Default toggle), 'HTTP' (URL: http://localhost:5000/api/grafanadashboard, Access: Server (default), Whitelisted Cookies: New tag (enter key to add) Add), 'Auth' (Basic auth, TLS Client Auth, Skip TLS Verify, Forward OAuth Identity, With Credentials, With CA Cert), and 'Custom HTTP Headers'.

Figure 73 – Grafana data source configuration

In order to function correctly, this data source needed the implementation of three different endpoints on the Flexigy back end.

- **GET /** - This endpoint is used to test the connection between the two components. The back-end API should respond with a 200-status code when queried.
- **POST /search** – Returns the available metrics when invoked. For example, all system devices.
- **POST /query** – This endpoint is triggered when a metric is picked, querying the back-end application for data.

Code snippet 11 shows part of the *GrafanaDashboardController* class, where all the needed endpoints are made available. For example, for the search endpoint, the system will query a specific Grafana service implementation that will return all the available system metrics, such as devices and prices, in a collection of strings.

```
public class GrafanaDashboardController : ControllerBase
{
    private readonly IGrafanaDashboardService _service;

    public GrafanaDashboardController(IGrafanaDashboardService service)
    {
        _service = service;
    }

    [Route("api/[controller]")]
    [HttpGet]
    public ActionResult<Boolean> TestConnection()
    {
        try
        {
            return Ok(true);
        }
        catch (Exception e)
        {
            return NotFound(e.Message);
        }
    }

    [Route("api/[controller]/search")]
    [HttpPost]
    public async Task<ActionResult> Search()
    {
        try
        {
            List<string> res = await _service.getGrafanaSearchResults();

            return Ok(res);
        }
        catch (Exception e)
        {
            return NotFound(e.Message);
        }
    }
}
```

Code Snippet 11 – GrafanaDashboardController class implementation

In the case of the query endpoint, all the time-series data returned by the back-end must strictly follow a 2D Array with values and the time. Table 17 shows an example of the response data structure. Note that the time must be a Unix timestamp in milliseconds.

Table 17 – Response data structure for the query endpoint

Energy	Time
0.56	1450754160000
0.23	1450754220000
0.44	1450754280000

Code snippet 12 demonstrates how the system translates this structure into a DTO object that will be used in the communications between the Flexigy back-end and the Grafana.

```
public class TimeSeriesResponseDto
{
    // FROM https://grafana.com/grafana/plugins/simpod-json-datasource/
    public string target { get; set; }
    public List<List<double>> datapoints { get; set; }

    public TimeSeriesResponseDto(string target, List<List<double>> datapoints)
    {
        this.target = target;
        this.datapoints = datapoints;
    }
}
```

Code Snippet 12 – TimeSeriesResponse DTO

Lastly, figure 74 shows a user dashboard interface in Grafana with the user Flex Offers scheduling and production energy profile.

Figure 74 – User dashboard interface

5.9 Chapter Summary

This chapter presented a proof of the implementation of the most important features developed during the internship. It also provided the reader a description of the platform setup and used technologies.

6 Solution evaluation and tests

This chapter describes the unit tests, the integration tests, and a test case used to experiment and evaluate the scheduling algorithms, as this was one of the most important features developed during the internship.

6.1 Tests

This section describes the methods used to test the Flexigy system in order to ensure that all requirements and constraints are met and to guarantee the accuracy and quality of the solution. Two different levels of tests were used: unit testing and integration testing. Unit testing is a software testing technique where small code portions or software components are tested individually [105]. xUnit [106] was the chosen tool to test the Flexigy platform as it provides unit testing capabilities for .Net Core systems.

Upon conclusion of unit testing, the integration between modules needs to be tested, which leads to integration testing. Integration testing aims to verify the functionality and reliability between integrated system modules [107]. Postman was the tool chosen to execute these tests as it provides testing capabilities for RESTful web APIs [108].

In figure 75, it is possible to see an example of an integration test performed in the Flexigy API in order to verify if the response to an invalid buyer profile was the expected one (line 3).

The screenshot shows the Postman interface for a REST client test. The URL is `http://localhost:5000/api/user` and the method is `POST`. The `Tests` tab is active, displaying the following JavaScript code:

```
1 |  
2 | pm.test("Body matches string", function () {  
3 |   pm.expect(pm.response.text()).to.include("An error occurred while creating the user - The entered  
   |     buyer profile does not exist");  
4 | });
```

Figure 75 – Integration test

Figure 76 shows an example of the successfully run integration tests done to assess the creation of different system entities.

RUN SUMMARY			1
▶	POST	Insert User	1 0
▶	POST	Insert Duplicate User	2 0
▶	POST	Insert User Invalid Buyer Profile	2 0
▶	POST	Insert User Invalid Supplier Profile	2 0
▶	POST	Insert Device	1 0
▶	POST	Insert Duplicate Device	2 0
▶	POST	Insert Device Invalid Type	2 0
▶	POST	Insert Device Invalid Name	2 0
▶	POST	Insert Device Invalid User	2 0
▶	POST	Insert Flex Offer Manually	1 0
▶	POST	Insert Flex Offer Manually Invalid Dates	2 0
▶	POST	Insert Flex Offer Manually Invalid Type	2 0
▶	POST	Insert Flex Offer Manually Invalid Name	2 0
▶	POST	Insert Flex Offer Manually Invalid Profile	2 0

Figure 76 - Integration tests for entities creation

6.2 Flex Offer scheduling algorithms evaluation

The section starts by presenting the approach to evaluate the developed algorithms, then the test data used is described, and, finally, the results are examined.

6.2.1 Approach

The approach adopted to assess Flexigy's ability to respond to the consortium Flex Offer scheduling requirements were:

- 1) Create a day worth of test data and register it in the system.
- 2) Run the algorithms.
- 3) Evaluate the results according to the consortium's initial constraints and goals.

6.2.2 Test data

The test data used to test the scheduling algorithms was a simulation of an energy community with five members, each with a different combination of data in order to cover the maximum possible cases. Table 18 resumes the test data used of the five community members.

Table 18 – Algorithm’s test data

User	Consumption Profile	Supplier Profile	Production	Flex Offers fixed	Flex Offers shiftable
User1	Cautious	Tactical	Sim	1	3
User2	Community	GoAhead	Sim	1	3
User3	Bold	Tactical	Não	1	2
User4	Cautious	Tactical	Não	1	2
User5	Bold	Tactical	Não	1	3

The following sections will detail each user test data further by showing the Flex Offers energy profile and, lastly, will present the daily price profile considered in the test.

6.2.2.1 User 1

User 1 is a Tactical self-producing user with a Cautious buyer profile. Figure 77 shows an overview of the user's four Flex Offers graphically while also showing the User forecasted production profile (top left).

Figure 77 – User 1 Flex Offers profiles

6.2.2.2 User 2

User 2 is a Go-Ahead self-producing user with four Flex Offers registered in the system. Figure 78 shows an overview of the user Flex Offers graphically.

Figure 78 - User 2 Flex Offers profiles

6.2.2.3 User 3

User 3 states three consumption Flex Offers in the system. Figure 79 shows an overview of the user information graphically.

Figure 79 - User 3 Flex Offers profiles

6.2.2.4 User 4

User 4 has three consumption Flex Offers registered in the system. Figure 80 shows an overview of the user information graphically.

Figure 80 - User 4 Flex Offers profiles

6.2.2.5 User 5

User 5 has four consumption Flex Offers registered in the system. Figure 81 shows an overview of the user information graphically.

Figure 81 User 5 Flex Offers profiles

6.2.2.6 Prices

Figure 82 shows the test prices for three different energy suppliers. The green line shows the price profile for community electricity, the orange price profile represents the prices for a renewable energies grid supplier, and the blue price profile illustrates a more traditional grid supplier.

Figure 82 – Price profile of three different energy suppliers for a given day test day

6.2.3 Results

This section will analyze and highlight some of the most important cases in the test data scheduling. Note that the Flex Offers energy profile will be illustrated in the background with a green color.

6.2.3.1 Level 1 Results

Given that User 1 has energy self-production and a Tactical supplier profile, it is expected that the Level 1 algorithm should be executed to maximize self-consumption on all its Flex Offers.

In figure 83, it is possible to depict that the Fixed Flex Offer presented, whose energy profile is illustrated in green, has been partially scheduled with the user’s self-production in Level 1, depicted by the yellow stripes in the figure.

Figure 83 – Level 1 scheduling of User 1 Fixed Flex Offer

Figure 84 shows the energy profile of a Shiftable Flex Offer of User 1. In this case, the schedule (yellow stripes) is due to start at 08:45 AM, as the algorithm calculated that this would minimize the estimated overall cost. Note that in this case, the Shiftable Flex Offer is not totally scheduled, thus its energy profile and type being updated for future Level 2 scheduling.

Figure 84 – Level 1 scheduling of User 1 Shiftable Flex Offer

Given the Go-Ahead supplier profile of User 2, it was expected that none of the user Flex Offers should be optimized during Level 1. Users 3, 4, and 5 do not have any self-production, so Level 1 is not executed for their Flex Offers.

Considering the comparison between the expected and obtained results, it is possible to say that Level 1 works as designed.

6.2.3.2 Level 2 Results

Regarding the Level 2 schedule, the result analysis will start at the User 1 Fixed Flex Offer showed previously in Level 1 (figure 83). Note that this user has a **Cautious** buyer profile, meaning the algorithm must minimize the overall price at all the time slices.

In figure 85, for example, it is possible to see that from 1:30 AM to 3:45 AM, the algorithm scheduled the consumption from the renewable Grid 1 supplier (orange). Meanwhile, from 3:45 AM onwards, the supplier chosen was Grid 2 (blue). If we recap the price profile for these hours, highlighted in figure 82, it is possible to see that, from 3:45 onwards, the cheapest supplier is, in fact, Grid 2, meaning the algorithm is working as supposed, minimizing the consumption price.

Figure 85 - Level 2 scheduling of User 1 Fixed Flex Offer

Considering User 1 Shiftable Flex Offer also seen at Level 1 (figure 84), it was expected that the energy surplus missing to fulfill the Flex Offer was scheduled in Level 2. In figure 86, it is possible to see that the remaining energy was scheduled using the Grid 2 supplier (the cheapest at that hour). In figure 87, both the self-consumption from Level 1 and the energy scheduled during Level 2 are combined, ultimately fulfilling the Flex Offer energy profile.

Figure 86 - Level 2 scheduling of User 1 Shiftable Flex Offer

Figure 87 – Comparison between the initial and scheduled Flex Offer energy profile

Given the Community Supporter profile of User 2, the algorithm should maximize the user community consumption. For example, in figure 88, it is possible to see a Shiftable Flex Offer schedule (orange) maximizing community energy sources. Note that when the community does not have enough energy to fulfill the Flex Offer, the surplus energy is scheduled using the cheapest supplier, in this case, Grid 2.

Figure 88 - Level 2 scheduling of User 2 Shiftable Flex Offer

Lastly, a Shiftable Flex Offer of User 3 will be analyzed. Note that this User has a Bold energy profile, which means the algorithm should only schedule energy consumptions from renewable sources. In figure 89, it is possible to see that the Flex Offer was totally fulfilled by Grid 1 energy supply, the cheapest among renewable energy suppliers at those hours.

Figure 89 - Level 2 scheduling of User 3 Shiftable Flex Offer

Considering the comparison between the expected and the analyzed results, it is possible to say that Level 2 works as designed.

6.3 Chapter Summary

This chapter described the strategies used to test and evaluate the developed solutions. It started by outlining the unit and integration tests done on the platform. Then, a test case for the scheduling algorithms was presented, and the results were discussed, proving the algorithms work as supposed.

7 Conclusions

This chapter recaps the most critical points of this work, presents the results obtained from the project's development, explains the project's limitations and future improvements, and gives a final appreciation of the project and the internship.

7.1 Summary

This project's goals were to improve the Flexigy platform on multiple aspects. First, a study of state-of-the-art solutions and technologies related to the project problem was conducted. This phase helped to better understand the energy unbalance problem caused by the increasing introduction of renewable energy sources in energy grids and its implications to the population in general.

Additionally, traditional answers to the problem, such as electricity storage and energy demand management services, were explored while also presenting related projects that contributed to the design of the Flexigy platform. Moreover, an analysis of the previous Flexigy prototype was conducted, enumerating its many limitations, such as its non-maintainable and non-scalable architecture.

Secondly, as demonstrated during the requirements engineering and analysis chapter 3, a collection of system functional and non-functional requirements were identified, leading to the modification of the previous implementation domain model.

Third, a whole reengineering process of the Flexigy system architecture was performed, which applied the Onion architectural pattern in order to make the new platform more usable, extendable, and maintainable (section 4.2).

Furthermore, the energy optimization algorithms based on the day-ahead Flex Offer schedule were architected, built, and tested, introducing a new multi-level execution architecture while also contemplating the new user's profiles and consortium constraints. As demonstrated in chapter 6, the implemented algorithms showed the expected results for both Fixed and Shiftable Flex Offers. As introduced in the work planning section 1.2, this feature was due to continue to be developed for a more extended time period, hence implementing the Elastic Flex Offer scheduling being one of the next steps in the internship.

Moreover, newly requested features such as a visualization platform or a service to handle interruptibility and regulating reserve requests were designed and developed during the project.

7.2 Accomplished goals

Table 19 summarizes the information by specifying a degree of accomplishment for each of the internship goals defined in the introduction section 1.1.1.

Table 19 – Internship goals degree of accomplishment

Goal	Degree of Accomplishment
Implement the Flexigy web platform accounting for system maintainability, scalability, performance, and ease of future integration whit VPS systems	Complete
Architect, build and test the flex-offers scheduling algorithms according to the defined consortium goals and business rules	Complete ¹
Add a feature that enables the Flexigy platform to handle EDM requests	Complete
Build a service to operate devices	Complete
Forecast building's unpredictable energy consumption based on historical consumption patterns	Complete
Visualize the various aspects of the application; most importantly, the Flex offers scheduling	Complete

¹ Note that tests are still ongoing to improve and optimize the existing algortihms and to access its performance.

7.3 Limitations and future development

Although the project is set to achieve all the initial goals, it is possible to enumerate some limitations and new features that could be implemented in the future.

- As stated during the report, some of the most critical system features heavily rely on the PV energy production forecasts to function correctly, thus making the implementation of this feature one of the priorities for future developments.
- Although there were a few devices connected to the platform, a bigger and more diversified device infrastructure could heavily benefit the platform development. For instance, a larger set of devices would allow a thorough performance and scalability test to the developed scheduling algorithms.
- The user can only create Flex Offers automatically for two different device types, which denotes a need to research and implement new algorithms to forecast the consumption of devices from other types. For example, if the system could recognize the device type and automatically generate its flexibility profile, reducing user inputs to the minimum, Flexigy would significantly improve the overall user experience.
- House batteries or even electric vehicle batteries serving as energy storage solutions could be a step forward for the platform scheduling algorithms. For instance, a battery could save all of the user energy production during the day to sell the energy later during peak demand, benefitting both the user monetarily and the grid, as this would act as a distributed energy balancing solution.

7.4 Final appreciation

Considering the platform's reengineering process, the new features added, the documentation produced, and the stakeholders manifested satisfaction during the project presentations, this project can be considered a success.

Nonetheless, even though the presented solution shows good progress to the consortium goals, there is still a lot of research and improvements that must be carried out to make the project ideas available for the masses, as described in section 7.3.

On a more personal note, working on a research project for a consortium of big companies in the area was a great learning opportunity. From learning new concepts related to smart grids to presenting the project to different stakeholders and interested parties, this internship contributed to an incredible experience that helped to develop technical and social skills.

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Appendix A - Project Planning

Table 20 - Project planning

Goal	Deadline
Propose and contribute to the design of a system architecture.	July 2021
Architect, build, and test the flex-offers scheduling algorithms according to the defined consortium goals and business rules.	September 2021
Implement a feature that automatically detects the building's unpredictable energy consumption based on historical consumption patterns.	July 2021
Build a service to turn devices On/Off.	July 2021
Add a feature that enables the Flexigy platform to handle energy demand management requests.	July 2021
Develop a way to visualize the various aspects of the application	July 2021

Appendix B – UC2 Sequence Diagram

Figure 90 - Sequence Diagram UC2: Create Device

Appendix C – Holiday Weighted Historical Data Method Implementation

```
private Dictionary<DateTime, List<Tuple<double, double>>> holidayWeightedHistoricalData(List<Measurement> orderedMeasurements, Dictionary<DateTime, List<Tuple<double, double>>> dict, DateTime tomorrow)
{
    foreach (var t in dict)
    {
        double holidayWeight = Program.WEIGHT_VALUE, weekendWeight = Program.WEIGHT_HALF_VALUE;
        foreach (Measurement m in orderedMeasurements)
        {
            if (m.measurementTime.Hour == t.Key.Hour && m.measurementTime.Minute == t.Key.Minute)
            {
                if (DateSystem.IsPublicHoliday(m.measurementTime, CountryCode.PT))
                {
                    t.Value.Add(new Tuple<double, double>(m.energy.value, holidayWeight));
                    if (holidayWeight > 0.5) holidayWeight = holidayWeight - 0.1;
                }
                else if (DateSystem.IsWeekend(m.measurementTime, CountryCode.PT))
                {
                    t.Value.Add(new Tuple<double, double>(m.energy.value, weekendWeight));
                    if (weekendWeight > 0.2) weekendWeight = weekendWeight - 0.05;
                }
            }
        }
    }
    return dict;
}
```

Code Snippet 13 – holidayWeightedHistoricalData method implementation

Appendix D – Weekend Weighted Historical Data Method Implementation

```

private Dictionary<DateTime, List<Tuple<double, double>>> weekendWeightedHistoricalData(List<Measurement> orderedMeasurements, Dictionary<DateTime, List<Tuple<double, double>>> dict, DateTime tomorrow)
{
    DayOfWeek otherDay;
    if (tomorrow.DayOfWeek == DayOfWeek.Saturday)
    {
        otherDay = DayOfWeek.Sunday;
    }
    else
    {
        otherDay = DayOfWeek.Saturday;
    }
    foreach (var t in dict)
    {
        double dayWeight = Program.WEIGHT_VALUE, otherDayWeight = Program.WEIGHT_HALF_VALUE;
        foreach (Measurement m in orderedMeasurements)
        {
            if (m.measurementTime.Hour == t.Key.Hour && m.measurementTime.Minute == t.Key.Minute)
            {
                if (m.measurementTime.DayOfWeek == tomorrow.DayOfWeek)
                {
                    t.Value.Add(new Tuple<double, double>(m.energy.value, dayWeight));
                    if (dayWeight > 0.5) dayWeight = dayWeight - 0.1;
                }
                else if (m.measurementTime.DayOfWeek == otherDay)
                {
                    t.Value.Add(new Tuple<double, double>(m.energy.value, otherDayWeight));
                    if (otherDayWeight > 0.2) otherDayWeight = otherDayWeight - 0.05;
                }
            }
        }
    }
    return dict;
}

```

Code Snippet 14 - weekendWeightedHistoricalData method implementation

Appendix E – Workday Weighted Historical Data Method Implementation

```
private Dictionary<DateTime, List<Tuple<double, double>>> workdayWeightedHistoricalData(List<Measurement> orderedMeasurements, Dictionary<DateTime, List<Tuple<double, double>>> dict, DateTime tomorrow)
{
    foreach (var t in dict)
    {
        double dayWeight = Program.WEIGHT_VALUE, otherWeekDayWeight = Program.WEIGHT_HALF_VALUE;
        foreach (Measurement m in orderedMeasurements)
        {
            if (m.measurementTime.Hour == t.Key.Hour && m.measurementTime.Minute == t.Key.Minute)
            {
                if (m.measurementTime.DayOfWeek == tomorrow.DayOfWeek)
                {
                    t.Value.Add(new Tuple<double, double>(m.energy.value, dayWeight));
                    if (dayWeight > 0.5) dayWeight = dayWeight - 0.1;
                }
                else if (!DateSystem.IsWeekend(m.measurementTime, CountryCode.PT))
                {
                    t.Value.Add(new Tuple<double, double>(m.energy.value, otherWeekDayWeight));
                    if (otherWeekDayWeight > 0.2) otherWeekDayWeight = otherWeekDayWeight - 0.01;
                }
            }
        }
    }
    return dict;
}
```

Code Snippet 15 - workdayWeightedHistoricalData method implementation

Appendix F – UC7 Decrease Consumption Sequence Diagram

Figure 91 - Sequence Diagram UC7: Decrease Consumption

Appendix G – UC7 Increase Consumption Sequence Diagram

Figure 92 - Sequence Diagram UC7: Increase Consumption

Appendix H – UC11 Sequence Diagram

Figure 93 - Sequence Diagram UC11: Show Flex Offer Schedule

Appendix I – UC12 Sequence Diagram

Figure 94 - Sequence Diagram UC12: Show User Energy Production Profile

Appendix J – UC13 Sequence Diagram

Figure 95 - Sequence Diagram UC13: Show Energy Price

Appendix K – System Setup

K.1 Flexigy back-end

To run the Flexigy platform, it is recommended to use an integrated development environment to execute the .Net Core code (Visual Studio Code was chosen for the development of this project) and run the SQL Server database.

If a new database is setup, the system connection string must be updated. To do so, access the *appsettings.json* file and change the *DefaultConnection* parameter to the new database connection string.

In order to execute the code for the first time on a machine, all the dependencies must be installed using the *dotnet restore* command. After running this command and after connecting to the database, the platform must create the database schema and update the database accordingly. To do so, run the *dotnet ef migrations add <name>* followed by the *dotnet ef database update* command.

The final step in the platform's configuration is to execute it by running the command *dotnet run*.

K.2 Grafana front-end

To run the Grafana visualization tool, the following steps must be followed:

- 1) Install the Grafana open-source tool locally on your computer (for more information, visit the Grafana official website <https://grafana.com/grafana/download>)
- 2) Access Grafana dashboard through a browser. Usually, the Grafana can be found at: <http://localhost:3000/>. When prompted by a login page, insert the default credentials (username: admin; password: admin).
- 3) Install the JSON plugin data source into your local Grafana (for more details, visit the link <https://grafana.com/grafana/plugins/simpod-json-datasource/>).
- 4) Configure the data source according to the setup guide in <https://dev.to/luckykosi/complete-guide-how-to-use-grafana-with-a-custom-node-api-2hd5>, only changing the URL to <http://localhost:5000/api/grafanadashboard>.

Appendix L – Level 1 Schedule Day-Ahead Fixed Flex Offers

```
private async Task<ProductionProfile> scheduleSelfConsumptionFixedFO(ConsumptionFlexOffer fo, ProductionProfile production, User user)
{
    DateTime auxTime = fo.toScheduleProfile.start;
    ScheduledFOProfile schedule = new ScheduledFOProfile(fo.toScheduleProfile.start, fo.Id.Value);
    List<EnergySlice> energyProfile = fo.getToScheduleEnergyProfile();

    bool flag = false;
    foreach (EnergySlice es in energyProfile)
    {
        double consumptionSurplus = getConsumptionSurplus(production, auxTime, es);
        //only when there is a production value in a timeSlice
        if (consumptionSurplus != es.maxEnergy)
        {
            flag = true;

            List<SourceEnergySlice> sources = new List<SourceEnergySlice>(
);
            sources.Add(new SourceEnergySlice("Self_Production", 0, es.maxEnergy - consumptionSurplus, user.Id.Value.ToString(), true));
            TimeSlice a = new TimeSlice(auxTime, sources);
            schedule.addSlice(a);
        }
        auxTime = auxTime.AddMilliseconds(Program.TIME_SLICES_MILLISECONDS);
    }
    if (flag)
    {
        production = await scheduleConsumption(fo, schedule, production);
    }
    return production;
}
```

Figure 96 - Level 1 Schedule Day-Ahead Fixed Flex Offers

Appendix M – Level 1 Schedule Day-Ahead Shiftable Flex Offers

```

private async Task<ProductionProfile> scheduleSelfConsumptionShiftableFO(ConsumptionFlexOffer fo, ProductionProfile production, User user)
{
    double consumptionPrice = Double.MaxValue;
    ScheduledFOProfile schedule = new ScheduledFOProfile(fo.toScheduleProfile.start, fo.Id.Value);
    for (DateTime i = fo.toScheduleProfile.start; i.CompareTo(fo.toScheduleProfile.end) < 0; i = i.AddMilliseconds(Program.TIME_SLICES_MILLISECONDS))
    {
        DateTime auxTime = i;
        ScheduledFOProfile auxSchedule = new ScheduledFOProfile(auxTime, fo.Id.Value);
        double sum = 0;
        List<EnergySlice> energyProfile = fo.getToScheduleEnergyProfile();
        foreach (EnergySlice es in energyProfile)
        {
            double consumptionSurplus = getConsumptionSurplus(production, auxTime, es);
            sum = sum + this.checkPrice(consumptionSurplus, auxTime, production);

            List<SourceEnergySlice> sources = new List<SourceEnergySlice>();
            sources.Add(new SourceEnergySlice("Self_Production", 0, es.maxEnergy - consumptionSurplus, user.Id.Value.ToString(), true));
            auxSchedule.addSlice(new TimeSlice(auxTime, sources));
            auxTime = auxTime.AddMilliseconds(Program.TIME_SLICES_MILLISECONDS);
        }
        if (sum < consumptionPrice)
        {
            schedule = auxSchedule;
            consumptionPrice = sum;
        }
    }
    if (schedule.hasSelfProduction())
    {
        production = await scheduleConsumption(fo, schedule, production);
    }
    return production;
}

```

Figure 97 - Level 1 Schedule Day-Ahead Shiftable Flex Offers

Appendix N – Level 2 Schedule Day-Ahead Fixed Flex Offers

```
private async Task<ProductionProfile> scheduleFixedFO(ConsumptionFlexOffer fo,
ProductionProfile production)
{
    DateTime auxTime = fo.toScheduleProfile.start;
    ScheduledFOProfile schedule = new ScheduledFOProfile(fo.toScheduleProfile.
start, fo.Id.Value);
    Device device = await _deviceRepo.GetByIdAsync(new Tag(fo.deviceId));
    User user = await _userRepo.GetByIdAsync(new Username(device.username));
    List<EnergySlice> energyProfile = fo.getToScheduleEnergyProfile();
    foreach (EnergySlice es in energyProfile)
    {
        if (es.maxEnergy != 0)
        {
            schedule = scheduleSlice(auxTime, es, schedule, user, production);
        }
        auxTime = auxTime.AddMilliseconds(Program.TIME_SLICES_MILLISECONDS);
    }
    production = await scheduleConsumption(fo, schedule, production);
    return production;
}
```

Figure 98 - Level 2 Schedule Day-Ahead Fixed Flex Offers

Appendix O – Level 2 Schedule Day-Ahead Shiftable Flex Offers

```
private async Task<ProductionProfile> scheduleShiftableFO(ConsumptionFlexOffer
fo, ProductionProfile production)
{
    double consumptionPrice = Double.MaxValue;
    ScheduledFOProfile schedule = new ScheduledFOProfile(fo.toScheduleProfile.
start, fo.Id.Value);
    Device device = await _deviceRepo.GetByIdAsync(new Tag(fo.deviceId));
    User user = await _userRepo.GetByIdAsync(new Username(device.username));
    for (DateTime i = fo.toScheduleProfile.start; i.CompareTo(fo.toSchedulePro
file.end) < 0; i = i.AddMilliseconds(Program.TIME_SLICES_MILLISECONDS))
    {
        DateTime auxTime = i;
        ScheduledFOProfile auxSchedule = new ScheduledFOProfile(auxTime, fo.Id
.Value);
        double sum = 0;
        List<EnergySlice> energyProfile = fo.getToScheduleEnergyProfile();
        foreach (EnergySlice es in energyProfile)
        {
            if (es.maxEnergy != 0)
            {
                auxSchedule = scheduleSlice(auxTime, es, auxSchedule, user, pr
oduction);
                sum = sum + auxSchedule.getPrice(auxTime);
            }
            auxTime = auxTime.AddMilliseconds(Program.TIME_SLICES_MILLISECONDS
);
        }
        if (sum < consumptionPrice)
        {
            schedule = auxSchedule;
            consumptionPrice = sum;
        }
    }
    production = await scheduleConsumption(fo, schedule, production);
    return production;
}
```

Figure 99 - Level 2 Schedule Day-Ahead Shiftable Flex Offers

Appendix P – Level 2 Schedule Energy Slice

```

private ScheduledFOProfile scheduleSlice(DateTime auxTime, EnergySlice es, ScheduledFOProfile scheduled, User user, ProductionProfile production)
{
    foreach (TimeSlice ts in production.timeSlices)
    {
        if (ts.time.CompareTo(auxTime) == 0)
        {
            switch (user.buyerProfile.profile)
            {
                case "Bold":
                    //better price among renewable sources
                    SourceEnergySlice auxCommunitySourceEnergySlice = ts.getCommunitySourceEnergySlice();
                    List<SourceEnergySlice> auxRenewableCommunitySources = scheduleSliceCommunityProfile(es, auxCommunitySourceEnergySlice, scheduled, ts.energySources, true);
                    scheduled = scheduleSliceBoldProfile(scheduled, es, auxRenewableCommunitySources, ts.energySources, auxTime);
                    return scheduled;
                case "Cautious":
                    //minimize price at all cost
                    SourceEnergySlice auxCommunitySec = ts.getCommunitySourceEnergySlice();
                    List<SourceEnergySlice> auxCommunitySources = scheduleSliceCommunityProfile(es, auxCommunitySec, scheduled, ts.energySources, false);
                    scheduled = scheduleSliceCautiousProfile(scheduled, es, auxCommunitySources, ts.energySources, auxTime);
                    return scheduled;
                case "Community":
                    //maximize the community consumption
                    SourceEnergySlice communitySec = ts.getCommunitySourceEnergySlice();
                    List<SourceEnergySlice> sources = scheduleSliceCommunityProfile(es, communitySec, scheduled, ts.energySources, false);
                    scheduled.addSlice(new TimeSlice(auxTime, sources));
                    return scheduled;
            }
        }
    }
    return null;
}

```

Figure 100 - Level 2 Schedule Energy Slice